

1 Review

2 Forward osmosis as concentration process: 3 opportunities and challenges

4 Gaetan Blandin^{1,2,*}, Federico Ferrari³, Geoffroy Lesage², Pierre Le-Clech⁴, Marc Héran², Xavier
5 Martínez-Lladó¹

6 ¹ Eurecat, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya, Water, Air and Soil Unit, Manresa, Spain.

7 ² Institut Européen des Membranes, IEM, Univ Montpellier, CNRS, ENSCM, Montpellier, France

8 ³ Catalan Institute for Water Research (ICRA), 17003 Girona, Spain

9 ⁴ UNESCO Centre for Membrane Science and Technology, School of Chemical Engineering, University of
10 New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia

11

12 * Correspondence: gaetan.blandin@eurecat.org

13 Received: date; Accepted: date; Published: date

14 **Abstract:** Although envisioned initially for desalination and energy production for which it showed
15 economics limitations, osmotic membrane systems like forward osmosis (FO) gain popularity as a
16 “soft” concentration process. FO features unique properties by combining high rejection rate, low
17 fouling propensity and can be operated without significant pressure or temperature gradient, and
18 therefore can be considered as a potential candidate for a broad range of concentration applications
19 where current technologies still suffer from critical limitations. This review extensively compiles
20 and critically assesses recent consideration of FO as a concentration process for applications
21 including food and beverages, organics value added compounds, water reuse and nutrients
22 recovery, treatment of waste streams and brine management. Fundamental aspects of mass transfer,
23 performances and limitations and design specific to concentration process are also described.
24 Encouraging potential is demonstrated to concentrate streams more than 20 fold with high rejection
25 rate of most compounds and preservation of added value products. For the applications dealing
26 with highly concentrated or complex streams, FO still features lower propensity to fouling
27 compared to other membranes technologies along with good versatility and robustness. However,
28 further assessments on lab and pilot scales are expected to better define the achievable concentration
29 factor, rejection and effective concentration of valuable compounds and to clearly demonstrate
30 process limitations (such as fouling or clogging) when reaching high concentration rate. Another
31 important consideration is the draw solution selection and its recovery that should be in line with
32 application needs (i.e. food compatible draw for food and beverage applications, high osmotic
33 pressure for brine management,...) and be economically competitive.

34 **Keywords:** Cold concentration; Food membrane process; Nutrients recovery; Water reuse; Brine
35 concentration

36

37

38 1. Introduction

39 Concentration processes are part of the main operation units in many industrial sectors like food
40 processing, mineral extraction, chemicals processing or environmental applications. Various
41 processes exist and their selection depends both on the properties of the stream to be concentrated,
42 requirements of the applications and final products. Those processes are classified in two main
43 categories, i.e. membrane and thermal concentration processes. Among membrane processes,
44 microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), are very broadly used and considered state of the art

45 separation technologies in various applications (food industry, chemical industries, water treatment,
46 etc...)¹. These technologies are of interests for all concentration processes that require the
47 concentration of molecules and particles with a particle size above 0.01 μm and up to 1 μm .
48 Typically, pathogens (bacteria, viruses, ...), organic macromolecules (proteins, carbohydrates, ...),
49 and minerals (clays, latex, ...) can be well rejected (and extracted or concentrated) by microporous
50 membranes. Its main advantage is the relatively low operating pressure (from 0.1 to 5 bar) and
51 therefore limited energy costs. High pressure membrane process such as reverse osmosis (RO) retain
52 the smallest organics (i.e. tannins, organic acids, polyphenols, pesticides, pharmaceuticals...), heavy
53 metals and salts. In comparison with thermal processes, RO proved to be less energy intensive,
54 requires less investment costs, lower footprint and avoids thermal degradation of compounds
55 (cooking taste) in food industry². One main disadvantage of RO is its inability to reach high
56 concentration levels due to the hydraulic pressure limitation. Current practices limit RO operational
57 pressure to 80 bar due to mechanical resistance and required energy. Another limitation of RO is the
58 fouling propensity when treating complex stream and given the high pressure operation³. As an
59 alternative to UF/MF and RO, nanofiltration (NF) features intermediate properties (operating
60 pressure, molecular weight cut-off) that allow rejection of compounds down to divalents ions and
61 with a variety of membrane characteristics that can make it a more adequate choice⁴. Membrane
62 distillation (MD) presents many attractive features, such as lower operating temperatures (<70°C)
63 compared to thermal processes, compact process, high rejection, not limited by osmotic pressure and
64 possibility to use waste heat⁵. However, MD, so far, remains at the pilot scale, as it is not energetically
65 and economically outperforming existing technologies (even when waste heat is used) and there are
66 no commercially available module for large scale applications⁶. Osmotic distillation (or osmotic
67 evaporation) is particularly suited for the processing of heat-sensitive aqueous solutions such as fruit
68 juices and pharmaceutical products. The solution to be concentrated is separated by a porous
69 hydrophobic membrane from a high osmotic pressure solution. OD was mostly tested for food
70 concentration^{2,7} but, as for MD so far, remains on pilot scale. Among thermal processed, evaporation
71 is an established treatment used in a broad range of applications. Main advantages of evaporation
72 are the relative low technology grade, low maintenance costs and the possibility to remove high
73 content of water. As main drawbacks, temperature sensitive compounds are altered by the high
74 temperature and evaporation require high amount of energy to produce heat. As alternatives, solar
75 evaporation allows operation at lower temperature but needs extensive surface (lagoons).
76 Cryoconcentration is a natural phenomenon which occurs during the ice thawing. More concentrated
77 phase is then separated from the initial solution. By avoiding high temperature treatment,
78 cryoconcentration technology can produce highly nutritive compounds, with biological and
79 organoleptic value⁸. However, commercial solution still requires remarkable energy consumption
80 and achievable concentration remains below that of evaporation⁹. Thus, to date, none of the existing
81 technologies has offered a fully satisfying solution allowing for high concentration rate at low energy
82 costs and without affecting the properties of the concentrated products.

83
84 Unique properties of FO rely on the following features¹⁰⁻¹⁴: (1) Dense membrane with high
85 selectivity and rejection of most compounds (like reverse osmosis (RO) membrane) enable to only
86 (mostly) extract water from the feed leading to high concentration rate; (2) No hydraulic pressure is
87 required for water permeation making the FO process as a soft technology; (3) The osmotic driven
88 force allows easier operation and does not require pressure vessels and expensive high pressure
89 pumps, FO can even be operated in submerged mode offering several design possibilities; (4) No
90 temperature gradient is required which also avoids degradation of feed compounds and at
91 minimised energy costs. FO is also called cold concentration; (5) Possible operation at very high
92 osmotic pressure allowing to treat already concentrated streams and reaching high concentration
93 ratios; (6) Treatment of viscous or charged/challenging feeds due to the lack of pressure or operation
94 in submerged mode; (7) Minimised fouling rate when operated at low flux and easy cleaning since
95 the fouling layer is not compacted on the membrane like in pressurised process. Thus, new
96 applications where current technologies showed limitations for extraction and purification of liquids

97 such as food concentration or complex streams like brines or highly concentrated wastewater (WW)
98 are envisioned for FO¹⁵. Following the intense FO research activities of the last decades, several
99 specific reviews discussed the interests, principles, limitations and challenges for future development
100 of the FO process. These reviews focused on mass transfer limitations^{16–18}, membrane
101 developments^{11,17}, fouling¹⁹, rejection of trace organic contaminants²⁰, optimized draw solutions^{17,21,22},
102 energy aspects^{18,23}, potential applications^{23–26} including WW treatment¹³, desalination²² and
103 hybridization of FO with other processes²⁵. However, no review has been dedicated to the specific
104 potential of FO as concentration process. FO can be a preferred candidate for concentration of streams
105 and an alternative to the established concentration processes which have some inherent drawbacks.
106 Numerous studies exist regarding concentration with FO for various type of applications (food
107 processing, recovery of value added organics, nutrients recovery from WW streams or concentration
108 of waste streams). The first part of this review therefore aims at compiling for the first time all studies
109 reporting FO operation as concentration process. Then, in a second part, the existing gaps in
110 knowledge both at a fundamental and practical levels towards FO implementation as concentration
111 process and the possible limitations to be overcome for broader developments of FO as concentration
112 process will be critically discussed.

113 2. Applications of FO as concentrating process

114 2.1. Food and beverages

115 2.1.1. Liquid food concentration

116 Vast amounts of liquid food are industrially concentrated to reduce storage, packaging, handling
117 and transportation costs²⁷. Thermal processing remains the most widely employed method for shelf-
118 life extension and food preservation and concentration²⁸. However, such technologies suffer from
119 serious drawbacks like high energy demand and loss of product quality (colour degradation,
120 “cooking taste”, loss of aroma) and its nutritive properties (vitamins, anthocyanins, carotenoids...)².
121 As an alternative, recent efforts have focused on (non-thermal) membrane processes; with UF and
122 MF being used for clarification or large molecular-weight compounds separation, and NF and
123 especially RO more dedicated to concentration as such thanks to their high rejection properties. The
124 benefits of RO in comparison with thermal technologies include better preservation of flavours and
125 aroma, lower energy and investment costs. As the main drawback, achieved concentrations remain
126 limited to 25–30° brix due to the high osmotic pressure of the concentrated product and limits in
127 hydraulic pressure operation of RO. Thus, to date, RO remains a pre-concentration process and could
128 not fully compete with evaporation to reach concentration rates of 45–65° brix².

129
130 The first attempt to use FO for liquid food was in 1966 but remained confidential²⁹; only in the
131 90s with the development of dedicated FO membranes, more intense research was initiated³⁰. A
132 broad range of liquid food was concentrated using FO: grape, raspberry, orange, pineapple, kokum,
133 grapefruit, jaboticaba, red radish, tomato, beetroot, coffee, sucrose^{28,31,32}. Early studies demonstrated
134 the proof of concept; orange and red raspberry juice were successfully concentrated with high acid
135 and colour rejection (>99.9%). FO concentrates with similar flavour and aroma than commercial
136 products were obtained^{33,34}. A significant amount of research on tomato juice concentration by
137 Petrotos & Lazarides^{27,35,36} confirmed generally positive results, but FO fluxes were limited to below
138 4.5 L.m⁻².h⁻¹. Following the development of dedicated FO membrane, several studies demonstrated
139 the possibility to concentrate the following: pineapple juice up to 60° Brix³⁷, Kokum juice from 2 to
140 52° Brix³⁸, beetroot, pineapple and grape juice from 2.3 to 52° Brix, 8.0 to 54.6° Brix and 4.4 to 54° Brix
141 respectively³⁹. Positively, observed permeation fluxes were mostly above 5 L.m⁻².h⁻¹ showing the
142 importance of dedicated FO membrane. Those studies confirmed the beneficial advantage of FO vs.
143 thermal processes in concentrating and avoiding degradation of valuable components such as
144 anthocyanin in Kokum, betalain in beetroot juice or ascorbic acid in pineapple. Reconstituted fresh
145 juice from those concentrates also proved to be very similar to initial fresh juice⁴⁰. Sant’Anna *et al.*

146 confirmed that FO preserved nutraceutical and organoleptic characteristics of the jaboticaba juice
 147 unlike thermal concentration which decreases anthocyanin and compounds with antioxidant
 148 capability, beyond of changes on beverage colour properties ³². Overall beneficial interests in flavor
 149 and nutritional properties preservation pushes the FO market towards an even broader range of
 150 liquid juice application (coffee concentration, bergamot juice, coconut milk, strawberry juice) ⁴¹⁻⁴³.
 151

152 Among the limitations of FO for food processes, the compatibility of the draw solution with the
 153 concentrated food juice needs special attention. Even if the FO membrane rejects most compounds,
 154 small fractions of the draw solution may permeate through the membrane and alter product flavours.
 155 Mostly sucrose/glucose and NaCl (Table 1) were used as draw solution but no study has reported
 156 impact on the juice concentrate. An *et al.* used potassium sorbate (a common preservative in the food
 157 industry) as draw solution thanks to its high osmotic potential and low reverse permeation flux. In
 158 their study, apple juice concentrate flavours were not altered and potassium sorbate in the juice
 159 concentrate was in line with legislation ⁴⁴. Another limitation is the membrane fouling and enhanced
 160 concentration polarisation that may occur especially with complex liquids and in the presence of
 161 proteins (pectins...) that can form a gel layer on the membrane surface. The application of ultrasound
 162 proved to be beneficial to mitigate gel layer formation in the context of sweetlime juice and rose
 163 extract anthocyanin colorant solution concentration and with minimal degradation of anthocyanin
 164 ⁴⁵. A recent study used a new generation of highly permeable thin-film composite (TFC) membranes
 165 for the concentration of grapefruit juice ³¹. Such membrane allowed for significant improvement of
 166 permeation flux (>10 L.m⁻².h⁻¹), testifying for recent progress in FO membrane development.
 167 Significant fouling propensity was observed but easily mitigated by pre-treatment to remove
 168 suspended solids. Also, membrane cleaning by simple physical washing allowed for sustainable
 169 operation.

170 Table 1: Review of research studies of liquid food reporting concentration factor (CF) using cellulose
 171 triacetate (CTA) and TFC membranes

Application	Membrane type	Draw solution	Initial Jw (L.m ⁻² .h ⁻¹)	Initial conc.	CF	Final conc.	ref.
Pineapple	CTA-FO	Sucrose/NaCl	<1	12 ^o	5	60 ^o	37
Kokum	CTA-FO	6M NaCl	12.3	2 ^o	26	52 ^o	38
Tomato	TFC-RO	4M NaCl	6	5.5 ^o	2.9	16 ^o	46
Grapefruit	TFC-FO	2M NaCl	13	100% juice	4	22 ^o	31
grapefruit	TFC-FO	2M glucose	13	100% juice	4	22 ^o	31
grape	CTA FO	6M NaCl	8.5	4.4 ^o	12.3	54 ^o	39
beetroot	CTA FO	6M NaCl	12.4	2.3 ^o	22.6	52 ^o	39
pineapple	CTA FO	6M NaCl	10.5	8 ^o	6.8	54.6 ^o	39
raspberries	CTA FO		10.5	10 ^o	4.5	45 ^o	34
Sweetlime	CTA FO	6M NaCl	9	11 ^o	4.5	50 ^o	45
sucrose	CTA	4M NaCl	5.8	10 ^o	5.6	56.8 ^o	47
orange press liquor	CTA	4M NaCl	16.8	8 ^o	1.3	10.5 ^o	48
Rose extract anthocyanin	CTA FO	6M NaCl	11	4 ^o	12.5	50 ^o	45

172 2.1.2. Dairy

173 Eliminating the water content in milk is an essential step during several dairy product
 174 manufacturing processes such as cheese, yogurt, concentrated milk and milk powder production⁴⁹.
 175 Dairy products are generally concentrated using multi-stage evaporators (concentration, to remove
 176 up to 90% of the water) followed by spray drying if powder is required⁵⁰. For example, concentrated
 177 milk dry matter content should be increased from 8-12% to 20-25%; in milk powder process milk is
 178 concentrated until 50% dry matter content before being sent to spray dryer⁴⁹. Overall, the production
 179 of whey powder and powder milk required the removal of water from raw milk (85.5-89.5%
 180 moisture) to reach 3-5% moisture in the final product⁵¹. Thermal concentration can affect the
 181 functional properties and digestibility of dairy heat-sensitive products and is energy intensive,
 182 accounting for the highest share of overall energy needed in the dairy industry^{50,52,53}. Membrane
 183 technologies were developed for dairy separation/fractionation (UF) and concentration (NF, RO)
 184 since their energy demand is much smaller than evaporation⁵⁴. However, given the osmotic pressure
 185 of concentrated dairy fractions, and hydraulic pressure to be exerted, membrane concentration can
 186 only reach a maximum dry weight of 12–20%. Thus, RO is mostly used as pre-concentration step
 187 before evaporation to reach the desired final concentration especially in the context of whey products
 188 ⁵³.

189 So far, FO studies dedicated to dairy processes remain scarce and focused on two steps: milk
 190 and whey concentration (Table 2). Only one FO study dedicated to skim milk concentration was
 191 reported. In that study performed on an 8'' pilot scale setup, the concentration objective of 2.5 fold
 192 was achieved (from 8 to 21% wt)⁵⁵, proving the feasibility to concentrate milk using FO. Passage of
 193 small organic molecules was detected, which caused foaming in the draw solution during the
 194 concentration process. Moderate fouling was observed in the conditions tested (flux below 10 L.m⁻².h⁻¹)
 195 and the cleaning protocol (citric acid followed by enzyme based solution cleaning) was able to
 196 completely restore the initial membrane performance.

197 Current efforts are developed to valorise whey and its valuable compounds through
 198 fractionation and concentration steps. Aydiner *et al.* conducted a series of studies on FO-RO hybrids
 199 for whey recovery and concluded that FO-RO can achieve high concentrations of whey (25-35%),
 200 high recovery of water for reuse and be economically competitive⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸. Wang *et al.*, using in-house
 201 made TFC HF membranes also reached 22% dry solids whey thanks to a CF of 3.6⁵⁹. Chen *et al.*
 202 evaluated whey concentration potential by FO, reaching a CF of 2.5 times and without significant
 203 change in dry product composition⁵⁵. This study also pointed out that significant energy savings can
 204 be achieved using FO instead of thermal processes or (standalone) RO; Of special interest, the
 205 potential use of saline brines (produced during the dairy process) as draw solutions avoids the
 206 necessity of draw recovery step which bring a significant advantage for FO implementation.
 207

208 Table 2: Review of FO concentration studies for dairy applications

Application	Membrane type	Draw solution	T (°C)	Initial Jw (L.m ⁻² .h ⁻¹)	Initial conc.	CF	Final conc.	ref.
Skim milk	CTA FO	0.9M NaCl	16-19	4.5	8%	2.8	22%	55
Whey	CTA FO	0.9M NaCl	16-19	4	5.9%	2.5	15%	55
Whey	TFC FO	0.5M NaCl	22.5	12	6%	3.6	22%	59
Whey	CTA FO	2M NaCl	25	28	6.8%	4	28%	57
Whey	CTA FO	2M NaCl	25	12	2.5%	8	21%	58
Whey	CTA FO	3M NaCl	25	20	6.8%	2.1	14%	56

210 2.1.3. Alcohol

211 Several research groups studied the possibility to separate alcohol, mostly ethanol, from water
212 through FO. The potential interest is both for alcohol purification in the context of its production or
213 the concentration or removal from beverages like beer or wine. FO advantage relies on the operation
214 at low temperature preserving taste and flavours and/or avoiding high energy costs of distillation.
215 The water/alcohol separation relies on the preferential affinity and diffusivity through the FO
216 membrane of one of the compounds; however, studies remain relatively scarce and not always
217 showing similar trends.

218
219 A first study evaluated the possibility for FO to concentrate ethanol (also called ethanol
220 dehydration, in the feed solution) with draw recovery via solar energy through a theoretical
221 approach. Concentration rate up to 50% ethanol purity seemed realistic but recovery as high as 95%
222 is not feasible due to high osmotic pressure required from the draw solution (e.g. 391 bar for 90%
223 ethanol concentration)⁶⁰. Zhang *et al.* investigated the use of FO for the concentration of bioethanol
224 using a CTA membrane and highly concentrated NaCl solution as draw (26%) and proved
225 experimentally that ethanol content could be increased from 15 to 27.8% and from 82.5% to 90.1%
226 thanks to the preferential permeation of water for the whole range of water/ethanol ratio tested. Even
227 though promising, this process suffered from loss of ethanol (forward ethanol flux), reverse salt
228 diffusion and degradation of the membrane after extended contact with concentrated ethanol
229 solution⁶¹. Using a similar membrane, different results were obtained by Ambrosini *et al.* who
230 demonstrated the possibility to preferentially remove alcohol from a feed solution (dealcoholisation).
231 This study performed with lower initial alcohol concentration in the feed (5%) described how draw
232 selection can impact relative alcohol/water passage through the membrane, organic draw solutes
233 being preferred to favor alcohol permeation⁶². The same research team also investigated the impact
234 of membrane type (CTA and TFC membranes from HTI) on the separation process⁶³. TFC membrane,
235 which comparatively rejected better ethanol, proved to be less relevant in the context of
236 dealcoholisation. Both alcohol dehydration and dealcoholisation and tunability to the application
237 needs are promoted by FO membrane suppliers as part of FO concentration processes in alcoholic
238 beverages^{41–43}. However, limited amount of studies are available and moreover sometimes
239 contradictory regarding preferential water and ethanol respective passage through FO membranes.
240 Further work is required to clearly assess the interest and limitations of FO in this application both
241 for alcohol concentration and dealcoholisation. Impact of initial alcohol/water ratio, type of draw
242 solution and membrane type as well are more fundamentals of understanding of mass transfer are
243 needed.

244 2.2. Organic value-added compounds

245 2.2.1. Food derived products and by-products

246 Organic value-added compounds, such as proteins, peptides, antioxidants, colorants, flavours
247 and dietary fibers can be recovered from food products or by-products (fruit, olive, dairy, cereals,
248 seafood, slaughterhouse...). Those products, also called nutraceuticals, can deliver health benefits on
249 top of their nutritional value⁶⁴. Recovery of those products relies on extraction (usually via solvent)
250 and separation/concentration steps that can be performed through membrane processes. Initial tests
251 with FO demonstrated the potential of this technology to concentrate 2 times a modelled solution of
252 bovin serum albumin⁶⁵. Then, several studies validated the concept on industrial by-products
253 streams (Table 3): 9 times concentration of polyphenols from carob pulp was achieved as part of
254 polyphenols process extraction and purification⁶⁶; proteins and minerals from tuna cooking juice
255 were also successfully concentrated by FO (from 4 to 9%)⁶⁷, 2.15 times polyphenols concentration
256 from olive mill WW⁶⁸, 3 to 4 times melanoidins and antioxidants concentration from molasses
257 distillery WW⁶⁹.

258
259 FO also proved to be of interest as a concentration process in the main production of anthocyanin
260 extract from *Garcinia indica* Choisy (popularly known as kokum), concentrated 54 times (from 49

261 mg/l to 2.69 g/l)³⁸. Sugar concentration is one of the targeted applications either for sugar juice
 262 production or downstream bioethanol production. Several studies confirmed the potential either
 263 using xylose as model solution⁷⁰ or real streams. Four-fold concentration of sucrose from sugarcane
 264 juice (from 10.5 to 40.6%)⁷¹ was achieved. In the context of sugar concentration for ethanol production
 265 from rice straw, FO proved to be beneficial in removing fermentation inhibitors and concentrating
 266 sugar from 199 up to 1612 mM and leading to improved production of ethanol^{72,73}. 5-fold
 267 concentration of fermentation products of commercial relevance (acetic acid, succinic acid, lactic acid
 268 and ethanol) was also achieved to facilitate their valorisation^{74,75}. Other applications are envisioned
 269 in the protein and pharmaceutical industry⁷⁶. Overall, most studies confirmed the high rejection of
 270 those organic compounds by FO membranes but also pointed out the need for adapted draw solution
 271 (not to pollute the feed stream) and indicated required pre-treatment and cleaning strategies to limit
 272 fouling potential of certain molecules (like pectins for example).
 273
 274
 275

Table 3: FO concentration studies on food derived products and by-products

Application	Membrane type	Draw solution	Initial Jw (L.m ⁻² .h ⁻¹)	Initial conc.	CF	Final conc.	ref.
polyphenols from carob pulp	CTA FO	K-lactate 60 ^g Brix	13	1.13 g.L ⁻¹ TPC & 4.5 ^g	16.2 (TPC)	18.4 g.L ⁻¹ TPC & 24.5 ^g	66
Proteins /tuna cooking juice	CTA FO	0.5-2M NaCl	5	5.5%	1.6	9.0%	67
Biophenols /olive mill WW	CTA FO	3M MgCl ₂	6.5	>2 concentration on analysed phenolic			68
Polyphenols & melanoidins /Molasses distillery WW	TFC FO	4M MgCl ₂	4	80 g.L ⁻¹ Mel, 10 g.L ⁻¹ Polyphenols	>2 concentration with 97% rejection of Melanoidins, 90% on antioxidant		69
Polyphenols & melanoidins /Molasses distillery WW	CTA & TFC	3M MgCl ₂	4-6	80 g.L ⁻¹ Mel, 69mM antioxydant	up to 4	141-267g.L ⁻¹ Mel, 102-213 mM antioxydant	77
Xylose	TFC FO	1-3M MgCl ₂ /LaCl ₃	25	25g.L ⁻¹	6	150g.L ⁻¹	70
sugar cane juice /sucrose	TFC FO	sea bittern (MgCl ₂)	13	10.50%	3.9	40.60%	71
rice straw /sugar	TFC FO	MgSO ₄ (saturated)		20g.L ⁻¹	3.6	72 g.L ⁻¹	72
pretreated-rice straw / sugars	TFC FO	3.6 M TEA	4	199mM	8.1	1612mM	73
fermentation broth/succinic acid	TFC FO	5M NaCl	16	40g.L ⁻¹	4.5	180g.L ⁻¹	74
fermentation broth / lactic acid	TFC FO	5M NaCl	13	15g.L ⁻¹	3.8	57g.L ⁻¹	74

fermentation broth	TFC FO	5M NaCl	22	20g.L ⁻¹	5.5	110g.L ⁻¹	74
/ ethanol							

276 2.2.2. Microalgae harvesting

277 Microalgae are sunlight-driven cell factories that convert carbon dioxide to potential biofuels,
 278 foods, food supplements, feeds, fertilizer and high-value bioactives compounds ^{78–80}. Two main
 279 streams for microalgae production exist: (1) well controlled indoor cultivation system in closed
 280 systems for high value product (food) and (2) lower cost open-air system for less stringent
 281 applications. Along with the potential for CO₂ sequestration, microalgae based WW treatment is a
 282 promising approach to remove pollutants and produce biogas, biofuels and feeds ^{81,82}. Harvesting
 283 microalgae is a major challenge because of their small size, their density similar to water and their
 284 low concentration in the culture medium⁸³. Currently, available processes involve two and more
 285 steps for concentration, including chemical or biological flocculation, centrifugation and / or
 286 filtration, as well as spray or thermal drying and extraction⁸⁴. Utilizing high energy intensive
 287 centrifuge system is economically justifiable only for high value-added product production⁸³. The
 288 use of membrane technology in microalgae cultivation, harvesting and processing surged as a
 289 promising alternative even though no commercial-scale application has been reported yet; hybrid
 290 processes (cultivation and separation) are very promising since they allow for process intensification
 291 ⁸³.

292 Microalgae is effective to remove N and P and is generally envisioned as tertiary WW treatment;
 293 although using a bacteria-microalgae consortium allow also for chemical oxygen demand (COD)
 294 removal^{85,86}. A recent review discussed applications of FO for microalgae which can be multiple⁸⁷;
 295 FO can be envisioned as harvesting technology (concentration up to 1-5%). When compared to other
 296 membranes (UF/MF), benefits of FO are the higher selectivity and nutrient removal rate from the
 297 water^{88,89}. FO can be implemented as a standalone concentration step for concentration or within a
 298 hybrid also known as osmotic membrane photobioreactor⁹⁰. Among FO initiative, the OMEGA
 299 Project evaluated the possibility to concentrate microalgae and harvest nutrients from WW using FO
 300 bags placed in seawater; concentration by 4 to 6.6 times were achieved in the lab and full scale
 301 demonstration was realised in real environment^{81,91}.

302
 303 Several bench scale studies using cross flow setup confirmed effective high removal of water
 304 and concentration of microalgae by FO; using novel TFC membrane, Ye *et al.* achieved more than 20
 305 times concentration (from 1 up to 23g.L⁻¹) at high flux (above 20 L.m⁻².h⁻¹) and without major fouling
 306 issues⁹². Among others, the use of human urine and glycerol was successfully used as draw solution
 307 for microalgae concentration (by 4 and 2.5 folds respectively)^{93,94}. Recently, Ryu *et al.* demonstrated
 308 the feasibility to concentrate microalgae up to 120 g.L⁻¹ using glucose solution that is effectively
 309 diluted to be used as nutrients for microalgae, avoiding the need for reconcentration process⁹⁵. Still,
 310 effective permeation flux and concentration are largely dependent on the operation. Spacerless FO
 311 module feed channel design or submerged systems proved to limit biomass loss in the filtration
 312 system^{92,96}. Biomass cultivating conditions and unexpected extrapolymeric substances production
 313 lead to enhanced fouling that is boosted by reverse salt diffusion (RSD) from the draw solution^{96,97}.
 314 As for other FO applications especially dealing with difficult streams, draw selection and membrane
 315 orientation with active layer facing feed (AL-FS) are key elements in FO microalgae concentration
 316 process^{92,97–100}

317 2.2.3. Volatile fatty acid production

318 An alternative method to the conversion of the organic fraction into energy as biogas is the
 319 production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs), which are building blocks for a multitude of valuable
 320 products such as biopolymers, medium, or long chain fatty acids and biofuels¹⁰¹. However, the
 321 generally low organic content of domestic WW (<300 mg L⁻¹) hinders efficient recovery and is one of
 322 the main limitations in developing feasible bioproduction platforms. FO was evaluated as pre-

323 concentration step; it enabled 10-fold dewatering of domestic WW, primary sludge and secondary
 324 activated sludge but part of the COD was lost due to aeration which promoted COD degradation¹⁰².
 325 Still, FO increased the soluble COD (sCOD) fraction in the sludge enhancing VFA production by 7%
 326 for secondary sludge and by 35% for primary sludge (from 10% to 45%) but did not enable VFA
 327 production from the domestic WW due to the limited sCOD. FO concentration of VFA produced in
 328 a hydrolytic anaerobic reactor was studied to optimize downstream microbial desalination cell
 329 (MDC)⁷⁵. VFA rejection by FO membrane was highly pH dependent¹⁰³; at pH=7.5 rejection rates above
 330 80% are achievable and therefore the concentration of VFA by FO process proved to be realistic and
 331 5-fold concentration from 60–80 up to 300–400 mg L⁻¹ was reached.

332 2.3. Water reuse and nutrients recovery

333 The use of FO within the WW treatment line has been extensively studied in the last decade with
 334 the primary objective to promote water reuse; FO acts as a strong barrier that allows purification and
 335 disinfection of water to be considered for this stringent application. Its implementation can be
 336 beneficial especially if a saline stream is available (seawater, fertilizer, industrial brine...) ^{104–106}. Using
 337 FO to combine water reuse and desalination (FO-RO hybrid) already demonstrated several
 338 advantages like the double barrier protection (FO and RO both use dense membranes) and can have
 339 positive economics compared to stand-alone seawater RO desalination, due to energy (osmotic
 340 dilution) and maintenance savings, resulting from lower fouling tendency estimated from laboratory
 341 or pilot scale testing ^{107–112}. Recently, a first large scale pilot demonstration plant (1000m³/day) has
 342 been launched in Yeosu (South Korea)¹¹³. Initial studies have considered tertiary treated WW as feed
 343 of the FO-RO hybrid. However, some recent lab-scale and pilot studies demonstrated that FO is a
 344 robust and simple process allowing to treat even difficult streams such as anaerobic digester
 345 concentrate or sludge ^{114,115}. Thus, instead of using tertiary or secondary treated WW, new concepts
 346 have emerged, including the implementation of FO upstream in the WW treatment scheme which
 347 can be beneficial not only in the context of water reuse but also for nutrients concentration to facilitate
 348 their downstream recovery (Figure 1).

349

350 Figure 1: Integration of FO as a concentration process in the WW treatment line to combine water reuse
 351 and nutrients concentration

352 2.3.1. Primary treated WW and raw sewage concentration

353 FO treatment is envisioned on the raw WW after primary treatment or on raw sewage (sewer
 354 mining)^{104,116}. The pre-concentration of low strength WW by FO when combined with anaerobic
 355 digestion, has several benefits including higher biogas production, recovery of nutrients, lower FO
 356 membrane fouling propensity, smaller digester volume¹⁰⁴. A large numbers of studies has been
 357 recently published relating interests, limitations and optimisation of such schemes ^{117,118}. Several
 358 studies have already tried to implement FO for pre concentrating WW for subsequent treatment via

359 anaerobic digestion. A first study by Zhang *et al.* achieved 6-fold concentration of primary treated
360 WW using a lab-scale CTA cross-flow module, leading also to a 3.1 fold COD concentration¹¹⁹. Ansari
361 *et al.* demonstrated the feasibility to concentrate by 10 fold WW and to reach 1000 mg.L⁻¹ COD
362 concentration which is suitable for downstream anaerobic digestion¹²⁰. Moving to pilot scale, water
363 concentration factors (WCF) of 5 and 2.5 were achieved with spiral wound membrane and submerged
364 plate and frame (P&F) TFC modules respectively^{121,122}. One of the limitations of raw WW
365 concentration is the incomplete and heterogeneous recovery of nutrients (N, P, COD). COD is
366 generally well rejected by the FO membranes (COD removal >97%), but both studies showed that in-
367 between 19.2% and 25.8% of the COD entering the system was lost due to biodegradation during the
368 filtration process or attached to the membrane surface. While elevated phosphorous recovery was
369 possible due to high rejection by the FO membranes, lower nitrogen recovery was observed resulting
370 from poor membrane rejection (up to 50-60%)^{119,122,123}.

371
372 Fouling is the main concern in membrane processes and especially when treating challenging
373 feeds. Fouling was observed in most studies and especially when reaching high CF¹²⁰. However,
374 initial experiments using FO on primary treated (screened) WW demonstrated that the accumulated
375 fouling layer was loose and easily reversible¹⁰⁴. Also, the concentration of raw sewage using
376 submerged FO system proved to be promising with operation without clogging and no major fouling
377 issue¹²¹. Another limitation of FO process concentration can be the toxicity of some compounds for
378 downstream treatments, i.e. anaerobic digestion inhibitors such as SO₄²⁻, NH₃, and salts. Apart from
379 limiting the CF, organic draw solution (sodium acetate or EDTA-2Na) with lower RSD and
380 biodegradability potential might be used¹²⁰. Still, filtration of WW and especially raw WW is as a
381 major operating challenge and most studies were performed in lab or small scale pilot with very
382 limited filtration time; Longer term assessment are required and are expected to reveal other
383 practical issues and challenges.

384 2.3.2. Osmotic membrane bioreactor (OMBR)

385 In OMBR¹²⁴, FO is implemented within the secondary (biological) treatment. Higher rejections
386 of contaminants were observed than for classical membrane bioreactor (MBR), yet at lower fouling
387 propensity¹²⁵⁻¹²⁷ and thus OMBRs can produce the high water quality which is crucial in the context
388 of potable water reuse and reject, degrade and/or concentrate most contaminants/nutrients including
389 trace organic contaminants^{127,128}. One major limitation of OMBR is the salinity build-up impacting
390 biological activity¹²⁹. To tackle this issue, the addition of UF or MF system into OMBR to create salt
391 bleeding is promoted. This process is more complex to operate since two sets of well-balanced
392 membrane systems are needed^{130,131} but can allow for concentration of phosphorous to facilitate its
393 downstream recovery^{132,133}. Another configuration is the implementation of FO on the MBR permeate
394 to avoid salinity gradient in the biological reactor; Xue *et al.* demonstrated the possibility to operate
395 such system for phosphorous and nitrogen concentration achieving up to 4 and 2.1 fold concentration
396 respectively when concentrating WW 4 times. According to modelling results, up to 10 folds of
397 nutrients concentration could be achieved by optimising conditions for nitrogen rejection and using
398 a ratio seawater(draw):WW of 2:1^{134,135}.

399 2.3.3. Anaerobic OMBR (AnOMBR)

400 Anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) is combining anaerobic digestion technology with
401 membrane technology. Unlike traditional anaerobic digestion, AnMBR allows the treatment of low
402 strength streams by decoupling the SRT from the HRT. In the last few years, many studies focused
403 on the direct treatment of municipal WW via AnMBR at lab and pilot-scale¹³⁶, but the low methane
404 production, the energy needed for the membrane operation (biogas sparging and permeate pump)
405 and for maintaining reactor temperature limited its broader development¹³⁷. Combining FO with
406 AnMBR has developed an increasing interest to increase COD load and improve biogas production.
407 These technologies can be combined in two different ways: (1) by replacing or coupling the MF or UF

408 membrane system with a FO system in an AnOMBR system or (2) by using FO to pre-concentrate
 409 WW for subsequent anaerobic treatment.

410
 411 Operation of AnOMBR positively led to almost total removal of COD and phosphorous and 62%
 412 removal of ammonium-nitrogen which is a bit higher than conventional AnMBR. Also, 0.21LCH₄.g
 413 COD⁻¹ of biogas was consistently produced even after salinity build up that did not seem to impact
 414 the biological activity¹³⁸. Similar observations than for OMBR were drawn, i.e. high rejection rates,
 415 moderate fouling but severe salinity build-up overtime when only a FO membrane is used ¹³⁹. Even
 416 if in some cases, biogas production did not seem impacted by salinity build-up, Tang *et al.* observed
 417 that it negatively affected methanogenic growth leading to ousting of methanogens by sulfate
 418 reducing bacteria¹⁴⁰. As for OMBR, combining FO and MF membrane into the AnMBR reactor was
 419 also evaluated and positively avoid salinity build-up while assuring production of high water quality
 420 (through the FO membrane), production of biogas and concentration of nutrients (phosphorous in
 421 the MF permeate) to facilitate its precipitation¹⁴¹.

422
 423 The water production cost associated with the combination of FO-RO-AnMBR for municipal
 424 WW treatment was estimated by Vinardell *et al.* ¹⁴² for four different scenarios, AnMBR directly
 425 treating WW and FO-RO-AnMBR with different FO water recoveries (50, 80, 90%). WW treatment
 426 cost below 1€·m⁻³ was achieved when FO recovery was limited to 50%; increasing FO flux above 10
 427 L·m⁻²·h⁻¹ was identified as a key factor to improve significantly the competitiveness of the FO-RO-
 428 AnMBR system.

429
 430 Table 4: Overview of FO integration in WW processes and efficiency in rejection or concentration of
 431 nutrients. TOC, COD, NH₄, TN and TP expressed in % removal or CF
 432

Process	membrane type	Draw solution	TOC removal (%) or CF	COD removal (%) or CF	NH ₄ removal (%) or CF	TN removal (%) or CF	TP removal (%) or CF	Ref.
OMBR	CTA (cross-flow)	NaCl 1M	98%	-	99%	-	-	143
	TFC (cross-flow)	NaCl 1M	96%	-	99%	-	-	143
	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	NaCl 0.7M	-	>99%	-	>82%	>99%	144
	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	NaCl and MgCl ₂	98%	-	80-90%	-	>99% (P-PO ₄)	145
	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	NaCl	>98%	-	>98%	-	-	146
	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	-	-	>95%	70-80%	-	>99%	147
An-OMBR	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	-	-	>95%	70-80%	-	>99%	139
	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	NaCl	-	96.7%	60%	-	99%	138
	TFC (Aquaporin)	MgSO ₄	-	>95%	>95%	-	>95%	148

	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	NaCl and Na ₂ SO ₄	92.9%	-	-	-	141	
WW pre conc.	CTA (sub-FO P&F)	-	-	99%	-	56-59%	99% (P-PO ₄)	106
	CTA (pilot-SW)	0.5 M NaCl	-	99.8%	48.1%	67.8%	99.7%	122
	TFC	Synthetic seawater brine	-	CF 2.4 & 2.7	CF 1.3 & 1.8	CF 1.6 & 1.9	CF 3.3 & 3.5	149
	CTA	Synthetic seawater	79.0 ± 6.7 %	-	85.4%	-	93.3 ± 3.3%	147
	CTA-ES	0.2-4M NaCl	-	96.5%	89.4%	93.3%	95.4%	150
	TFC- Aquaporin	1.5 M MgCl ₂	-	99%	CF 1.32	-	68-74%	151
	TFC	-	-	93.0- 97.5	<59.06%	-	93.71- 98.53% (P-PO ₄)	123
	CTA	1M NaCl	-	97%	-	96%	>99%	152
	TFC Aquaporin	1M NaCl	-	97%	-	96%	>99%	152
	CTA	0.6M NaCl	98%	-	70%	-	90%	153
	TFC (sub-FO P&F)	0.2M Seasalts	-	CF 2.4	CF 0.75	-	CF 2.2	121
	CTA	synthetic seawater	-	80-95%	89.2%	-	99%	154

433 2.4. Treatment of waste streams

434 2.4.1. Sludge concentration

435 Sludge produced during purification processes of WW generally requires to be concentrated
 436 through successive steps such as thickening, dewatering and possibly drying and stabilisation steps
 437 such as anaerobic digestion or liming before reuse or disposal. Those steps are energetically intensive
 438 and require chemicals; the opportunity to use osmotic energy for their concentration may be of
 439 significant economic interest.

440
 441 When FO was applied on aerated biological sludge, up to 7 folds concentration of MLSS was
 442 achieved (from 3 to 21g.L⁻¹) and with a high retention rate (>96%) of nitrogen and phosphorous
 443 allowing for the production of high nutrient sludge¹¹⁵. The potential of FO as thickening step was
 444 also demonstrated by Zhu *et al.* where MLSS could be increased from 7 to 39 g.L⁻¹ so to favour
 445 downstream anaerobic digestion efficiency¹⁵⁵. To limit RSD occurring with NaCl or seawater as draw
 446 solution, several studies investigated concentration with alternative draws. Na₃PO₄ proved to be a
 447 suitable draw agent allowing for sludge concentration from 3.5 up to 22 g.L⁻¹ with 100% phosphate
 448 rejection and concentration from the feed and low RSD (0.07g.L⁻¹)¹⁵⁶. Similar trends were observed
 449 using Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as draw with high rejections of feed nutrients and
 450 concentration of sludge from 8 up to 32 g.L⁻¹ ¹⁵⁷.

451

452 Following thickening step, aerated sludge at 7 g.L⁻¹ was further concentrated up to 35% dry
453 solids content using thin bed dewatering FO system¹⁵⁵. Most studies observed cake layer formation
454 and fouling propensity given the concentration rate of suspended solids achieved. However, in most
455 cases fouling was easily reversible even in the case of minerals precipitation. Still, antifouling
456 strategies should be envisioned especially in the case of sludge dewatering where cake formation is
457 inherent to the process. The application of ultrasound for fouling mitigation proved to impact sludge
458 flocs; mitigation of fouling deposition was observed only under mild/controlled conditions,
459 continuous ultrasound radiation applications may cause high organic release from sludge flocs and
460 thus leading to higher fouling rate^{158,159}. Module scale testing considering adapted module design to
461 tackle clogging and high solids concentration issues and anti-fouling strategies are still to be
462 evaluated to further assess the potential of FO for sludge concentration.

463 2.4.2. Urine recovery and concentration

464 Despite its low volumetric load (less than 1% of the all WW volume), it accounts for
465 approximately 80% of the nitrogen, 50% of the phosphorus and 55% of the potassium load in most of
466 the WW treatment plants¹⁶⁰. Separating urine from domestic WW promotes a more sustainable
467 municipal WW treatment system¹⁶¹. Moreover, phosphorus and nitrogen contents could be mined ;
468 human urine has often proven to suitable raw material for fertiliser production. However, most of
469 the urine diverting toilets or male urinals result in dilution of 2 to 10 times, which decreases its
470 efficiency for further recovery and reuse¹⁶². Several physicochemical and biological processes have
471 been developed for nutrient recovery and/or removal from urine, such as struvite precipitation,
472 ammonia stripping, and nitrification–denitrification process, and generally require high energy,
473 chemical and investment costs¹⁶³.

474
475 Several recent studies demonstrated the potential of FO as concentration/separation process for
476 ammonium and phosphorous recovery from source separated urine. Feasibility of urine
477 concentration by FO was demonstrated, with up to 5-fold concentration using 5M NaCl solution¹⁶⁴.
478 If phosphorous and potassium are concentrated, one main challenge is the relative poor rejection of
479 nitrogen especially under urea form by FO membranes (50–60%)¹⁶⁴. In that context, improved
480 rejection of nitrogen (50–80%) in hydrolysed urine was observed in comparison with low rejection of
481 neutral organic nitrogen (urea-N) in fresh urine¹⁶¹. pH adjustment around 7 also favoured higher
482 rejection of ammonium (around 80%)¹⁶⁵ by avoiding stripping of ammonia occurring at higher
483 natural pH of urine (above 8) and limiting potential membrane scaling¹⁶⁶. The concept has been
484 integrated within a FO-MD hybrid for the simultaneous production of fresh water and urine
485 concentration^{166–168}. Given the moderate rejection of urea by FO membrane, Volpin *et al.* combined
486 FO concentration process with fertigation by using a Mg based fertiliser as draw solution. In such
487 scheme, urine passing through the membrane enriches the fertilizer with ammonium while
488 phosphorous, remaining nitrogen and magnesium are concentrated on the feed side and can be
489 recovered as struvite precipitate^{162,169}; the revenue of such scheme being potentially more than 5 times
490 the associated (operational and capital) costs.

491 2.4.3. Landfill leachate

492 Thanks to its low exploitation and capital costs, landfilling is a widely used process for disposing
493 municipal solid waste. Landfill implies the generation of leachate, a highly polluted WW that must
494 be treated prior to discharge¹⁷⁰. Landfill leachate typically contains high amounts of organic matter,
495 ammonium, heavy metals, chlorinated organic and inorganic salts rendering its treatment complex and
496 expensive. Several approaches mentioned FO as a concentration step of the treatment train to lower
497 costs and enhanced recovery of nutrients and water¹⁷¹. Long term pilot testing demonstrated that FO
498 system (coupled with RO for draw recovery) could concentrate by 10 fold landfill leachate before
499 further crystallisation and solidification with cement which was returned to the landfill¹⁷². By
500 concentrating by 3.2 folds through FO, Iskander *et al.* observed that incorporating FO and humic acid
501 recovery into a Fenton's oxidation system-FO could decrease leachate volume, lower reagent

502 requirements, and reduce the sludge production by 30%¹⁷³. Even at a moderate concentration rate
503 (1.5 fold), and after calcium pre-treatment, FO was used to successfully precipitate struvite¹⁷⁴. FO
504 combined with microbial desalination cells also proved to be feasible to concentrate leachate and
505 recover nitrogen^{175,176}. Several other studies demonstrated the positive impact of FO as part of
506 leachate treatment line to produce fresh water and remove contaminants within FO-MD hybrid, FO-
507 fertigation or as post-treatment of MBR permeate, even though the CF in FO is not generally
508 mentioned^{177–179}.

509 2.4.4. Digestate treatment

510 Digestate in some cases can be applied onto farmlands to enhance crop yields as it is abundant
511 in nutrients (COD, N, and P)¹⁸⁰. However, in some areas, digestate production exceeds the carrying
512 capacity of lands nearby or is sometimes polluted. Thus, technologies focused on concentration
513 and/or nutrient recovery from digestate have been studied recently^{180,181}. Digestate from various
514 sources (potato starch WW, swine manure and two types of cattle manure) were comparatively tested
515 for concentration to enhance anaerobic digestion (side stream FO-AnMBR); 1.3 fold CF allows for
516 significant enhancement of biogas production¹⁸². Other studies evaluated the possibility to reject and
517 concentrate organic fraction, N and P from manure digestate using FO; even if manure CF was limited
518 to 2 in most cases, effective concentration of nutrients was achieved. P rejection was high in all cases
519 (>95%) but very variable rejection of nitrogen was observed from less than 40% in some cases and up
520 to nearly total rejection without clear explanation^{183–186}. P can be recovered as struvite if precipitation
521 is controlled; otherwise, it may lead to scaling issue^{185,187}. Li *et al.* mentioned that FO implementation
522 prior to struvite precipitation with MgCl₂ showed superior performance in P recovery and can
523 generate a value of 1.35 \$.m⁻³ thanks to recovered struvite and water¹⁸⁴. The possibility to recover
524 phosphate from sludge digestate concentrate was also successfully achieved by concentrating the
525 streams up to the limit of solubility so to precipitate phosphorous as calcium phosphate¹⁸⁸ or struvite
526 (using MgCl₂ as draw)²⁶. Fouling propensity was moderate in all cases even though it can be
527 explained by low permeation flux and by limited time of operation (few hours) and at lab-scale. The
528 fate of heavy metals and antibiotics from manure was also evaluated¹⁸⁴; heavy metals were highly
529 rejected by FO membranes while antibiotics are more membrane and compound dependent. Overall,
530 both antibiotics and heavy metals tend to accumulate in the concentrated stream and should be
531 considered for downstream treatment and applications.

532 2.5. Brine management: concentration and salts mining

533 2.5.1. Brine concentration /towards zero liquid discharge

534 Brines are produced by water desalination system (concentrate from RO of brackish and
535 seawater desalination plant) and from various industrial sectors (mining, pulp and paper, food
536 industry, chemicals...). The proper disposal/management of brines, and their highly concentrated
537 salts, organics, and other contaminants, represents a significant environmental challenge to most
538 plants¹⁸⁹. RO brines, especially inland brines still require appropriate management solutions¹⁹⁰.
539 Conventional disposal options for concentrate are surface water discharge, discharge to the WW
540 treatment plant, deep well injection, evaporation ponds and land application¹⁹¹. However, these
541 brine disposal methods are unsustainable and restricted by high capital costs. Nowadays, brine
542 treatment towards zero liquid discharge (ZLD) approach providing water reuse and waste volume
543 minimization is promoted¹⁹². Among other innovative processes, FO is gaining attention for brine
544 concentration. Among the few academic studies found^{193–195}, concentration from 73 up to 180 g.L⁻¹ via
545 an NH₃/CO₂ FO membrane brine concentrator (MBC) was achieved on produced waters from natural
546 gas extraction operations¹⁹⁵. This process allowed for higher concentration than high pressure RO
547 and 42% energy less than mechanical vapor compression evaporator. 90% water extraction from
548 brackish water brine was also obtained using FO, higher than MD for similar stream¹⁹⁴. Full
549 competitiveness versus existing concentration processes is still to be demonstrated on large scale and
550 ways of improvement remain especially with regards to flowrates and module design¹⁹⁶. Despite

551 relatively little literature, FO based brine treatments towards ZLD systems are now commercialised
552 ^{197–199}.

553 2.5.2. Seawater and brine mining/ recovery of valuable minerals

554 Given the continuously increasing issues of land-based mining industries with regards to
555 depletion of high-grade ores, important water and energy demand and environmental issues,
556 seawater and brines, containing large quantities of valuable minerals mining, become an attractive
557 alternative option to harvest minerals²⁰⁰. Apart from salt (NaCl), several minerals such as Na₂SO₄,
558 Li and Mg have been identified as specific targets and economically attractive^{200,201}. Main methods
559 identified for recovery of minerals are solar evaporation, electrodialysis, membrane distillation-
560 crystallization, adsorption/desorption; but novel membranes technologies including osmotic
561 processes such as pressure retarded osmosis or FO potentially have a role to play towards extraction
562 and concentration of minerals ^{201,202}. Scientific studies remain limited and focused on salt lake brines;
563 the possibility to concentrate Li (and Mg) by 2.8 folds (from 0.78 to 2.8 g.L⁻¹)²⁰³ and to integrate FO
564 and crystallisation for precipitation as lithium carbonate were demonstrated²⁰⁴

565 3. Tuning FO process for optimum concentration

566 3.1. Better understanding of FO fundamentals in the context of concentration

567 Most studies refer to rejection, concentration of feed component or % of water recovery.
568 However, performances of the processes are sometimes difficult to assess and compare due to the
569 lack of uniformed terminology and systematic methodology. Overall, concentrations of compounds
570 from the feed depends on the concentration of water and then on their fate during the concentration
571 process; phenomena such as partial rejection by the membrane, adsorption, biological degradation,
572 deposition of precipitation may happen during the concentration by FO, influencing the
573 concentration of those compounds. The following section aims first at proposing a methodology to
574 properly assess concentration of water and nutrients/contaminants in FO process. At first, WCF as a
575 key element for evaluation for effective concentration will be introduced. Then, current knowledge
576 of rejection of both mineral and organic elements by FO membranes will be reported as well as
577 potential effect such as biodegradation and deposition/clogging that may affect effective recovery.

578 3.1.1. Water concentration factor

579 The WCF represents the concentration of the feed solution at a given time and is calculated using
580 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.:**

$$581 \text{ WCF} = \frac{V_{Fi}}{V_F(t)} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

582 With V_{Fi} the feed initial volume and $V_F(t)$ the feed volume at any moment (t) during the filtration.

583 Of specific interest is the achievable WCF (WCF_a) which corresponds to the theoretically achievable
584 WCF when osmotic equilibrium is reached. Such factor is of specific interest to design the
585 concentration process and is a function of feed and draw solutions initial osmotic pressures and
586 volumes. Assuming that the membrane is only permeable to water, **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen
587 de la referencia.** is used to calculate the osmotic pressure at equilibrium, π_{equ} :

$$588 \pi_{\text{equ}} = \frac{(V_{Fi} * \pi_{Fi}) + (V_{Di} * \pi_{Di})}{V_{Fi} + V_{Di}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

589 With π_{Fi} , π_{Di} and V_{Di} being initial osmotic pressure of the feed solution, initial osmotic pressure
590 of the draw solution and initial volume of the draw solution respectively. Assuming there is no loss
591 of salts, V_{Fequ} , volume of the feed solution at the equilibrium can be calculated using **¡Error! No se
encuentra el origen de la referencia.:**

$$V_{Fequ} * \pi_{equ} = V_{Fi} * \pi_{Fi} \tag{Equation 3}$$

592 WCF_a can be then calculated at the equilibrium by using V_{Fequ} as value of V_{F(t)} at the equilibrium:

$$WCF_a = \frac{1}{\pi_{Fi}} * \frac{(V_{Fi} * \pi_{Fi}) + (V_{Di} * \pi_{Di})}{V_{Fi} * V_{Di}} \tag{Equation 4}$$

593 Based on **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, estimations on WCF by FO can be
 594 approximated. In Figure 2 are reported various configurations and the impact of operating conditions
 595 on the theoretically achievable WCF using batch operation. The impact of initial feed concentration,
 596 initial draw concentration, ratio feed/draw volume as well as the imperfect rejection of the draw
 597 solution by the membrane (RSD) are evaluated. It is important to understand that such model does
 598 not consider filtration kinetics or module design and only relies on batch operation (i.e. defined
 599 volumes and concentrations of feed and draw are implemented and the WCF_a is achieved when
 600 osmotic equilibrium after indefinite time is reached in between the two solutions).

601
 602 Figure 2: Modelling of WCF_a as function of (a) draw solute concentration and initial feed osmotic
 603 pressure (feed draw ratio 1), (b) feed draw ratio and draw osmotic pressure for $\pi_F=1$ bar

604 As observed in **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, WCF_a higher than 100 can
 605 theoretically be achieved. Obviously, the highest WCF_a corresponds to the conditions where initial
 606 feed concentration is minimal, initial draw solution concentration is the highest, and feed to draw
 607 ratio is minimal. In practice, WCF higher than 100 is rarely aimed and could be limited by other
 608 process limitations like scaling, viscosity, or very long kinetic especially when approaching the
 609 osmotic equilibrium. 10-fold concentration rate is achieved for a broad range of operating conditions
 610 and is a more realistic target for FO as concentration process. Refined model needs to consider RSD
 611 and ideally also forwards solute flux (FSD) which are key parameter affecting the WCF_a since any
 612 leakage of solutes will decrease osmotic gradient and shift the osmotic equilibrium. It is expected that
 613 at low WCF, RSD has a minimal impact but becomes critical when WCF>10 is expected.

614 3.1.2. Nutrients rejections and recovery

615 Large molecules like proteins (typically above 1000 kDa) are highly rejected by FO membranes
 616 and high CF were achieved (section 2.1). Pectins and humic acids feature very high molecular weight;
 617 tannins and polyphenols are smaller molecules (500-4000 Da) but still well above cut-off of FO
 618 membranes. However, imperfect rejection by FO membranes of small organics like VFA, alcohols,
 619 pharmaceuticals and ions (cations especially, ammonium and nitrate more specifically) has been
 620 reported^{20,103,205,206}. Overall, if the predominance of steric rejection is assumed for large molecules,
 621 other mechanisms may become preponderant for small ones, typically for molecular weight below
 622 400 Da. Specific rejection studies regarding low MW organics by FO were limited even if in general
 623 rejection remains high, some compounds were poorly rejected (sometimes below 50%) under specific
 624 operating conditions (pH, membrane and draw type) especially for compounds below 100 Da

625 (ethanol, acetic acid, urea, phenol) or some uncharged micropollutants even larger than 200 Da
626 ^{75,103,207–210}. Electrostatic interactions in-between the membrane and feed solutes are also to be
627 considered. While CTA membranes have a negligible charge, the TFC membrane surface features
628 carboxyl groups more negatively charged, which could serve as fixed ionic group, thereby conferring
629 the membrane a cation exchange feature²¹¹. Several studies demonstrated that negatively charged
630 membranes better rejected negatively charged compounds/anions while positively charged/cations
631 ones were more poorly rejected^{207,212,213}. Using TFC membrane and NaCl as draw, Ferrari *et al.*
632 observed a very strong effect of cations/anions selectivity, most cations present in the WW being
633 poorly rejected (NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) while anions (SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}) were effectively concentrated¹²¹.
634 Additionally, bidirectional solute flux plays a role ^{212,214,215}. When an ion with high diffusivity passes
635 through the FO membrane, the system tries to maintain solution electroneutrality by transporting the
636 less diffusive counter-anion; the low diffusing ion being the limiting one for the diffusion of both
637 counter ions^{215,216}. A similar phenomenon occurring for both directions, some electrostatic interactions
638 may occur in-between feed and draw ions, i.e. a draw electrolyte composed of a low-diffusivity cation
639 and high-diffusivity anion may promote the forward transport of feed anions and retarded that of
640 feed cations. Conversely, the forward transport of feed anions may be greatly reduced, while that of
641 the feed cation significantly enhanced. Such phenomenon, also referred as Donnan equilibrium, was
642 evidenced especially for rejection of nitrate and ammonium, draw selection having a great impact in
643 favouring or retarding their forward diffusion ^{206,212,214}. In addition to Donnan equilibrium, D'haese
644 mentioned frictional phenomena also called draw steric hindrance by Xie *et al.* as a potential
645 mechanism impacting forward solute flux ^{217,218}. pH of the solution to be concentrated does have a
646 role in ion transport for TFC membranes. As explained in the study by Lu *et al.*, when the pH of the
647 solution facing the active layer increases from 3 to 6, protonated carboxylic groups are substituted by
648 deprotonated carboxylic groups which make the negatively charged membrane surface influencing
649 electrostatic interactions ²¹². A couple of studies related to VFA rejection by FO also demonstrated a
650 strong pH dependence of the rejection and on their effective concentration. At pH 4, below VFA's
651 pKA, rejection relies solely on steric rejection while at pH above 6, VFA exist mostly as negatively
652 charged ions (R-COO^-); electrostatic repulsion with the negatively charged membranes significantly
653 enhanced VFA rejection ^{75,103}. In the case of uncharged compounds (no electrostatic interactions),
654 hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity may have a role in organic compounds rejection. It was demonstrated
655 that hydrophobic compounds may be adsorbed on the hydrophobic membrane surface. However,
656 high rejections due to adsorption are typically only a temporarily effect, until membrane saturation
657 occurs ²¹⁹; then adsorbed molecules may be transported to a higher extent due to their higher partition
658 coefficient ²²⁰. Reversely, D'haese demonstrated that small hydrophilic organics (like alcohols) may
659 show negative rejection (up to 4-5 times concentration in the permeate), their transfer being promoted
660 by salting out ²⁰⁵.

661
662 While FO systems treating WW have always demonstrated high COD and PO_4^{3-} rejection (Table
663 4), diverse levels of cations rejection. Among cations, NH_4^+ rejection is of major concern as it is of
664 interest for many applications connected to the recovery of water and nutrients from waste streams.
665 Poor NH_4^+ selectivity by TFC membranes is of major concern due to the extremely similar polarity
666 and hydraulic radius between NH_4^+ and water molecules¹¹⁸. Nitrogen recovery by FO suffers from
667 imperfect rejection not only as NH_4^+ form but also as NO_3^- or urea demonstrating that electrostatic
668 effect is not the only rejection mechanism in that case^{121,167,206}. Of interest in concentration processes,
669 Van Wyk reviewed the state of the art and conducted experiments to better assessed Lithium and
670 boron rejection and associated mechanisms²¹⁰. In opposition to TFC RO membrane which can feature
671 typically 90% boron rejection²²¹, studies conducted in FO reported lower and very variable rejection
672 (from 10 to 100%). Boron rejection is generally higher using active layer facing feed solution (AL-FS)
673 membrane orientation (higher electrostatic rejection), can be improved by dedicated membranes and
674 increase at higher pH when boric acid is converted in borate anions which have a higher hydrated
675 radius which favors steric rejection^{222–226}. Van Wyk confirmed the possibility to reach high rejection
676 of boron (>90%) using TFC membrane in AL-FS mode even at neutral pH²¹⁰. Lithium rejection was

677 first assessed by Coday *et al.* who observed a 78-88% efficiency with a TFC FO membrane²²⁷. This
678 range of value was confirmed by Van Wyk who observed higher rejection of lithium when operating
679 in active layer facing draw solution (AL-DS) membrane orientation and concluded that lithium
680 rejection was driven by electrostatic interactions and steric rejection²¹⁰.

681
682 Apart from the imperfect rejection by FO membranes, deposition or biodegradation may alter
683 effective concentration of organic compounds. Ferrari *et al.* indicated that up to 15% of COD was lost
684 during concentration of raw WW in submerged FO reactor¹²¹. Natural degradation of COD during
685 filtration (20 hr in that case) was found to be the most probable cause. In the context of VFA
686 concentration, Blandin *et al.*⁷⁵ also observed limited recovery (70-80%) of acetic acid due to
687 biodegradation over filtration time. Long filtration time, formation of a biofouling layer consuming
688 highly biodegradable VFA and contact with air were found to be all factors affecting VFA imperfect
689 recovery. Implementation of pretreatment to limit biofouling and periodic cleaning were applied to
690 limit VFA biodegradation. Onyshchenko *et al.* also reported ineffective concentration of microalgae due
691 to deposition in membrane spacers during FO filtration⁸⁸. Using spacerless channel or submerged
692 operation were proposed as improved design to limit deposition^{95,96}.

693
694 Very importantly, reduction of the rejection with increasing recovery was observed especially
695 for compounds like urea that was imperfectly rejected by FO membranes; this was expected since
696 high recovery results in an increase of the solute concentration in the module²⁰⁹. Such observation is
697 key for concentration process and reinforces the need for high rejecting FO system. Further studies
698 are required to assess specific rejection of organic compounds to be recovered both at a fundamental
699 level to understand mechanisms for rejection and using real feed solution that may consider
700 complexations of those compounds.

701 3.2. Membranes and modules

702 The parameters used to characterize these membranes are typically the pure water and salt
703 permeability of the rejection layer (factors A and B, respectively), and the structural parameter of the
704 support layer (S). The ideal FO membrane features a high A value (high water flux), low B (low salt
705 passage), low S (to limit internal concentration polarization, ICP) and sufficient mechanical strength
706 to support industrial operation at moderate pressure¹⁶. Huge membrane development was and still
707 is conducted regarding novel membrane focusing both on the membrane active and support layers
708 to improve permeability, selectivity and limit internal ICP¹¹. Overall, findings from academic
709 research have been translated into the development and commercialization of several FO membranes
710 with improved flux and selectivity (up to 30 L·m⁻²·h⁻¹ and with RSD below 0.5 g·L⁻¹ when using 1 M
711 NaCl draw solutions). Further improvement are desired but developing membranes with enhanced
712 selectivity rather than higher flux are required especially for poorly rejected compounds like NH₄⁺.
713 In the context of NH₄⁺ recovery, modifying the active layer with polyethylenimine (PEI), due to its
714 abundant positively charged amines, allows to increase by 15-25% the NH₄⁺ removal efficiency²²⁸.
715 High NH₄⁺ rejections of 97%, comparable to CTA membranes¹⁸³ was also observed with TFC
716 membrane enriched with Aquaporin selective water channel proteins which only allow water to pass
717 through and reject ions.

718
719 Among the challenges to overcome in FO, module design is certainly of high importance. An
720 ideal FO module is a trade-off between (1) a maximised surface area (i.e., high packing density), (2)
721 a minimised pressure drop and (3) limited ECP and particle deposition^{13,110}. Three different designs
722 are currently commercial, i.e. P&F, hollow fibre (HF) and spiral-wound (SW) module
723 configurations²²⁹⁻²³³. Tubular membrane configuration is under development but not commercialised
724 yet²³⁴. Among the challenges of cross flow module scale operation especially treating complex or
725 concentrated stream, is the necessity to transfer the feed solution through the modules and the
726 associated fouling/clogging issues. SW modules can be optimised by adjusting feed spacer type to
727 the stream to be treated, plate and frame may be operated without spacer, hollow fibre/tubular

728 membranes by adjusting inner fibre diameter. Still, deposition can occur and pre-treatment may be
729 required. Another option is the development of submerged configurations, as for MBR, where the
730 FO membranes are immersed in the feed solution and are less affected by clogging^{121,235}. Additionally,
731 this configuration, owing to its limited shear stress for applications, may be of interest for cultivation
732 of bioproducts, and concentrations to avoid breakage of fragile biological compounds²³⁶.

733

734 Both experimental and computational fluid dynamics work at the module scale, demonstrated
735 the need to improve the understanding of process limitations that could be affected both by channel
736 design and pressure balance in FO modules^{230,237–245}. Further studies are required with specific focus
737 on concentration process with regards to practical operation and limitations.

738 3.3. Process design

739 When comparing FO with other membrane filtration processes, one key element is the absence
740 of hydraulic pressure for water permeation that has important implications in term of process design.
741 First, operating at low pressure does not require mechanically resistant materials like in NF/RO and
742 therefore associated CAPEX cost are limited. Moreover, it allows more flexibility on the process and
743 module design and arrangements²⁴⁶. In FO, in opposition to NF/RO typically limited to spiral wound
744 cross flow modules, several other module designs can be envisioned like plate and frame, hollow
745 fibre, tubular and submerged modules. Main implication especially for tubular and submerged
746 modules is the opportunity to treat complex streams without major risk of clogging or extended pre-
747 treatment required¹²¹. Another implication is that pressurisation of the feed solution, which is a large
748 part of energy consumption and overall operation costs in NF/RO is not a limiting factor for process
749 design. Thus, one pass through modules in continuous mode is no necessary, FO system could be
750 operated either in batch or continuous mode. Designing osmotic process with multi-stage and
751 various draw driving forces during the concentration process is also more flexible than when done
752 with hydraulic pressure. While FO process was initially operated at low flux due to first generation
753 of membrane performances, novel TFC membranes suffer less from low flux comparison with
754 regards to other membrane technologies. Also, since operation at higher flux led to more fouling
755 propensity, recent studies on FO technologies at the module(s) scale identified several
756 recommendations for its optimum integration with the objective to operate at constant driving force
757 (and flux) rather than providing concentrated draw solution at the beginning of the FO process where
758 the feed solution has the lowest salinity and therefore the osmotic driving force is the highest.

759

760 One recommendation is to operate FO in counter current mode so to maintain a more constant
761 osmotic pressure over module(s) (Figure 3,²⁰⁹). Such approach of operating offers the double benefit
762 of (i) avoiding elevated flux at the start of the concentration process and so limiting the fouling
763 propensity and (ii) to still maintain a flux at the end of the concentration process instead of having
764 difficulties when reaching the osmotic equilibrium^{241,242}. Phuntsho *et al.* demonstrated that operating
765 in counter-current allows for higher average permeation flux and water extraction rate for the same
766 filtration area^{243,247}. Even more interesting, this mode of operation allows to shift the osmotic
767 equilibrium to increase the extraction capacity of a draw solutes and therefore the concentration
768 capacity of the feed stream²⁴⁷. As a final step for concentration, pressure assisted osmosis may be
769 used to overcome osmotic equilibrium limitations and reach higher concentration level if required
770 ²⁴⁸.

771

772

Figure 3: Description of osmotic pressure of feed and draw stream in along a FO module depending on operation in co and counter current (adapted from²⁰⁹)

773

774

775

776

777

778

779

780

781

782

783

784

785

786

If FO concentration may be considered as one step process (even under multiple stage operation), at a lab scale (lab scale/pilots) or even for some applications, recirculation of the concentrated feed stream may be preferred. In that case, concentrated feed coming out of the FO system is mixed with the inlet feed stream and concentration occurs progressively with feed volume constantly decreasing in the feed tank. If high CF is aimed, process design should consider feed tank and piping allowing to operate with a broad range of volume (ideally conic tank, limiting piping volume, adapted sensors). In existing studies (lab, pilot scale), draw side is either operated similarly in batch (with decreasing osmotic pressure occurring with dilution) or at constant draw osmotic pressure (reconcentration by topping up with a highly concentrated draw solution or using a reconcentrating draw solution process (RO, MD,...)). One could also think in operating with increased draw concentration over the concentration process at a lab scale level, mimicking counter-current continuous operation of full scale process.

787

3.4. Draw selection

788

789

790

791

792

793

794

795

796

797

798

Taking advantage of the osmotic gradient, FO on its own can be considered as a low energy process and only requires limited energy for stream circulation within FO modules. However, pure water extracted from the feed solution is only transferred to a (draw) solution with a higher osmotic potential, and as such, is rarely usable as is, applications for which FO can be used as a stand-alone process without draw regeneration are limited¹¹⁰. The draw regeneration requires the use of a second process which is generally energy intensive (RO/NF/MD, thermal process, etc.). An ideal draw solution must have the following characteristics: allowing for high water flux, minimal reverse draw solute flux, no toxicity, reasonably low cost, easy and low-cost recovery and compatible with feed purpose (facing the draw salt diffusion risk. Numerous studies reported various draw solutions and draw recovery process^{21,249,250}. Draw selection in the context of concentration will involve specific consideration of the following elements:

799

800

801

802

803

804

805

806

807

808

809

810

- Osmotic pressure should be in line with the required concentration level and the initial osmotic pressure of the feed solution to be treated. Required osmotic pressure will not only impact the draw selection but also the draw recovery method since above 60bar, typical RO recovery is limited and thermal process such as MD, evaporation processes or under development thermo responsive draw solution and processes are required²⁵¹.
- Compatibility with the solution to be treated is critical, especially for food and beverages or potable water reuse applications; non-food draw solution may simply not be approved. Also, RSD may alter taste or other organoleptic properties. RSD can be a limiting factor also with regards to achieving high recovery (by shifting the osmotic equilibrium) or may alter biological activity (by excess of saline compounds).
- Costs are very application-dependent. If in food and beverages or brine concentration, more flexibility in draw selection and recovery may be allowed thanks to the relative

811 low cost of FO vs. other concentration process; in lower costs applications, like in WW
812 treatment, low cost solution will be preferred^{252,253}.

813 3.5. Fouling, mitigation and cleaning

814 Fouling mechanisms in osmotic processes were extensively reviewed by She *et al.*¹⁹. Lower
815 fouling behavior, commonly accepted in FO in comparison with pressure driven system is currently
816 a hot topic of debate^{107,254–257}. It was demonstrated that low fouling behavior in early studies was the
817 consequence of operating at a low permeation flux (below 10 L.m⁻².h⁻¹); more severe fouling is
818 observed when operating at higher flux, demonstrating also the existence of a critical flux in FO
819 ^{127,258,259}. This has important implications for FO competitive advantages and optimized operation
820 especially for concentration purposes where highly concentrated streams are processed. Designing
821 systems with moderate but constant osmotic driving force are preferred to systems with initial high
822 osmotic gradient. Membrane cleaning techniques are similar to those employed for RO and NF for
823 cross flow modules using physical cleaning by flushing²⁶⁰, chemical cleaning^{261,262} or those of MBR
824 like air/gas scouring and vibration for submerged FO processes^{235,263,264}. Specific to FO, osmotic
825 backwashing (by similarity to hydraulic backwashing in pressure driven membranes) proved to be
826 the most promising technique especially used in combination with flushing by detaching the fouling
827 layer from the membranes and facilitating its diffusion (or flushing) away from the membrane
828 surface^{256,265}. Overall, even when operated at higher flux and enhanced fouling conditions, FO fouling
829 is relatively easy to remove using osmotic backwashing²⁵⁸. However, enhanced fouling behavior are
830 expected when reaching high CF and associated highly concentrated streams, but this impact has not
831 been specifically evaluated in the literature which typically operate fouling tests at low/moderate
832 water recovery.

834 In concentration process especially treating challenging streams scaling, biofouling and clogging
835 should be carefully addressed. Scaling is the precipitation of sparingly soluble salts which occurs
836 when reaching the limit of solubility. If mechanisms are similar to those of organic fouling, the
837 occurrence and severity of scaling is strongly dependent on the concentration and solubility of
838 potential scalants (or their precursors) in the feed solution and on the CF that is achieved²⁶⁶. Typical
839 scaling in membrane processes is linked to calcium (calcium sulfate, calcium phosphate and calcium
840 carbonate) or silica that may limit the recovery and concentration of the feed stream^{19,267,268}. Scaling
841 can also be enhanced by salt diffusion within the membranes (reverse or forward) that can locally
842 increase the content of scaling ions and supersaturation^{269,270}. Alkaline scale (calcium phosphate or
843 carbonate formation) might be limited by acidification of the solution²⁷¹; tuning the more appropriate
844 draw solution might also mitigate scaling propensity.

846 Biofouling refers to the attachment and propagation of living microorganisms, present in the
847 feed solution, to the membrane surface utilizing nutrient from the surrounding environment to form
848 a biofilm which can colonize all the surface¹⁹. Biofilm formation can occur even with low initial
849 amounts of microorganism but is promoted when reaching high concentration since nutrients are
850 more concentrated. Biofouling can also be enhanced by nutrients RSF from the draw solution¹⁹. In
851 addition to the loss of permeation flux, biofouling can also lead to the biodegradation of nutrients
852 from the feed solution, negatively impacting effective concentration (of VFA for example)⁷⁵.
853 Biofouling mitigation, especially when treating highly concentrated streams is of key importance and
854 should be mitigated by limiting filtration time, avoiding the presence of air and by implementing
855 efficient biofouling mitigation cleaning⁷⁵.

857 Finally, synergetic effects of organic fouling, scaling and biofouling were also observed further
858 enhancing cake formation, decreasing filtration^{272–274}; all those effects being even more critical when
859 concentrating feed solutions, it is a key aspect in FO process concentration system that requires
860 specific assessment. Also, most studies so far were performed at lab or small pilot scale configuration
861 during several hours up to several days of operation. Given the challenging stream to be

862 concentrated, fouling phenomena will surely occurs on a larger scale and longer term operation.
863 Clogging issues will certainly arise as well but so far has not been considered in the literature.
864 Assessing fouling and clogging issues is a major consideration to fully evaluate applications of FO in
865 concentration process and requires specific work.

866 4. Concluding remarks and future research

867 Concentration appears to offer great opportunities for FO for a broad range of applications given
868 its unique properties of high rejection rate and soft concentration process. Also, FO advantage relies
869 on its possibility to concentrate complex streams of a range of compositions and initial concentration
870 and up to high rates . Given those elements, FO appears to be more relevant and competitive where
871 value is justified by the compounds to be concentrated, rather than by the water which is extracted.
872 This explains current commercial push towards the recovery of high value compounds (food and
873 beverage, brine concentration...) rather than water reuse and desalination processes. Still several
874 considerations remain towards successful future FO implementations.

875 4.1. Need for dedicated concentration studies

876 This review also highlighted the fact that FO for concentration requires specific consideration
877 both at the fundamental level, lab scale evaluation and full-scale validation. Most studies found in
878 the literature were performed at bench scale using membrane coupon or small modules and with
879 limited operation time (few hours to few days). Given the challenging stream to be concentrated,
880 fouling phenomena will surely occur on a larger scale and longer term operation. Also, rather than
881 evaluating the rejections of specific compounds, studies should consider the CF and defining
882 limitations when reaching high concentration rates. Very rarely, studies were performed until the
883 theoretical limit or requirements of the applications. Additionally, those studies need to consider not
884 only the fraction of extracted water or the final concentration of the product but also analyze and
885 report the effective concentration of the compounds targeted as due to imperfect rejection,
886 biodegradation and deposition poor recovery can be observed. Finally, operating until high CF will
887 emphasize other potential limitations of FO such as viscosity, enhanced fouling, clogging or scaling
888 that will limit process viability and require proper technical answers such as adapted cleaning
889 procedure or required pre-treatment that has been rarely considered in existing literature on FO
890 concentration.

891 4.2. Design of FO concentration units

892 At the full scale level, FO offers a broad range of possibilities of operational design such as feed
893 and draw transfer in modules (co or counter current), modules arrangements, modules types
894 crossflow or submerged), operation in batch or one pass are key parameters that have to be further
895 evaluated. One critical aspect of FO concentration process is the design of units (feed and draw tanks,
896 module arrangement) that will allow appropriate operation during feed volume variations . This
897 represents some challenges from lab scale to industrial design. CFD and numerical analyses will help
898 to improve mass transfer, new modules design and arrangements. Lab and small pilot scale
899 experiments are also required to define optimized operation parameters (level of pretreatment,
900 optimized membranes and modules design to favour high recovery and avoiding compounds losses
901 or degradation).

902
903 Another important consideration is the draw solution. Operation with an available high osmotic
904 pressure stream that does not require regeneration or recovery will largely favour FO economics;
905 however, in most cases, this will not be possible and draw type and recovery system selection will
906 need to be implemented. Testing and selection of draw solutions will have to better consider level of
907 final concentration desired, suitability with applications (especially for food and beverages) and
908 associated solution for draw recovery.

909 4.3. To demonstrate competitiveness versus other concentration processes

910 As shown in Table 5, FO appears as a promising alternative to existing concentration process
 911 versus competitive technologies. One key advantage is the operation at ambient temperature which
 912 does not alter organoleptic properties of the products to be treated which is a key element especially
 913 for temperature sensitive components (food and beverages, pharmaceuticals, etc..). Interestingly also,
 914 relying on osmotic pressure, high CF could be reached, higher than RO and similar to thermal
 915 processes. Energy needs in FO depends on draw recovery type, osmotic pressure required and level
 916 of concentration to be achieved; there some competitive advantages are expected (especially vs.
 917 thermal processes) but are still to be confirmed through pilot/full scale studies. If confirmed, FO
 918 becomes attractive for food/beverage applications as well as for ZLD and mining from waste streams.
 919 Potential in mining from wastewater combined with water reuse seems more challenging but full
 920 economic evaluation is still to be performed considering not only benefits of water reuse but also on
 921 savings in the WW treatment line. The availability/synergy with existing saline streams in that
 922 context, limiting draw recovery costs is a key element in that context to support FO implementation.
 923 Still, FO technology is only at its infancy, slowly reaching the market and has to demonstrate its
 924 potential in full scale both in term of technical performances and operation.
 925

926 **Table 5: Comparative properties and performances of concentration processes**

	UF/MF	NF/RO	MD/OD	Evaporation	Cryo- concentration	Forward osmosis
Temperature	Ambient	Ambient	Moderate	High	Low	Ambient
Pressure	Moderate	High	No	No	No	No
Concentration capability		Limited	high	high	medium	high
Organoleptic preservation	Good	Good	Good- moderate	Poor	Good	good
Applications	WW, food, waste streams, desalination	WW, food, waste streams. desalination	Desalination (MD) / food (OD)	Food, Desalination	Food	WW, food, waste streams, desalination
Energy	Moderate	High	Low-high	Very high	high	low-high
Technology readiness level	Established technology	Established technology	Pilot scale	Established technology	Established technology	Reaching market

927

928 **Funding:** This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation
 929 programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 712949 (TECNIOspring PLUS)” and the
 930 Government of Catalonia’s Agency for Business Competitiveness (ACCIÓ)

931 **Conflicts of Interest:** “The authors declare no conflict of interest.”

932 **5. References**

933 (1) Eykamp, W. Chapter 1 Microfiltration and Ultrafiltration. In *Membrane Science and Technology*; Noble, R.
 934 D., Stern, S. A., Eds.; Membrane Separations Technology; Elsevier, 1995; Vol. 2, pp 1–43.
 935 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-5193\(06\)80003-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0927-5193(06)80003-3).
 936 (2) Jiao, B.; Cassano, A.; Drioli, E. Recent Advances on Membrane Processes for the Concentration of Fruit
 937 Juices: A Review. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2004**, *63* (3), 303–324.
 938 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2003.08.003>.

- 939 (3) Wenten, I. G.; Khoiruddin. Reverse Osmosis Applications: Prospect and Challenges. *Desalination* **2016**,
940 391, 112–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2015.12.011>.
- 941 (4) Mohammad, A. W.; Teow, Y. H.; Ang, W. L.; Chung, Y. T.; Oatley-Radcliffe, D. L.; Hilal, N.
942 Nanofiltration Membranes Review: Recent Advances and Future Prospects. *Desalination* **2015**, 356, 226–
943 254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.10.043>.
- 944 (5) Alkudhiri, A.; Darwish, N.; Hilal, N. Membrane Distillation: A Comprehensive Review. *Desalination*
945 **2012**, 287, 2–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.08.027>.
- 946 (6) Kiss, A. A.; Readi, O. M. K. An Industrial Perspective on Membrane Distillation Processes. *Journal of*
947 *Chemical Technology & Biotechnology* **2018**, 93 (8), 2047–2055. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.5674>.
- 948 (7) Hongvaleerat, C.; Cabral, L. M. C.; Dornier, M.; Reynes, M.; Ningsanond, S. Concentration of Pineapple
949 Juice by Osmotic Evaporation. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2008**, 88 (4), 548–552.
950 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2008.03.017>.
- 951 (8) Aider, M.; de Halleux, D. Cryoconcentration Technology in the Bio-Food Industry: Principles and
952 Applications. *LWT - Food Science and Technology* **2009**, 42 (3), 679–685.
953 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2008.08.013>.
- 954 (9) Cassano, A.; Jiao, B.; Drioli, E. Production of Concentrated Kiwifruit Juice by Integrated Membrane
955 Process. *Food Research International* **2004**, 37 (2), 139–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2003.08.009>.
- 956 (10) Akther, N.; Sodiq, A.; Giwa, A.; Daer, S.; Arafat, H. A.; Hasan, S. W. Recent Advancements in Forward
957 Osmosis Desalination: A Review. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2015**, 281, 502–522.
958 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.05.080>.
- 959 (11) Klaysom, C.; Cath, T. Y.; Depuydt, T.; Vankelecom, I. F. J. Forward and Pressure Retarded Osmosis:
960 Potential Solutions for Global Challenges in Energy and Water Supply. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, 42 (16), 6959.
961 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3cs60051c>.
- 962 (12) Jian-Jun, Q.; Lay, W. C. L.; Kekre, K. A. Recent Developments and Future Challenges of Forward
963 Osmosis for Desalination: A Review. *Desalination & Water Treatment* **2012**, 39 (1–3), 123–136.
964 <https://doi.org/10.5004/dwt.2012.2965>.
- 965 (13) Lutchmiah, K.; Verliefde, A. R. D.; Roest, K.; Rietveld, L. C.; Cornelissen, E. R. Forward Osmosis for
966 Application in Wastewater Treatment: A Review. *Water Research* **2014**, 58, 179–197.
967 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2014.03.045>.
- 968 (14) Rastogi, N. K. Opportunities and Challenges in Application of Forward Osmosis in Food Processing.
969 *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition* **2016**, 56 (2), 266–291.
970 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2012.724734>.
- 971 (15) Coday, B. D.; Xu, P.; Beaudry, E. G.; Herron, J.; Lampi, K.; Hancock, N. T.; Cath, T. Y. The Sweet Spot of
972 Forward Osmosis: Treatment of Produced Water, Drilling Wastewater, and Other Complex and Difficult
973 Liquid Streams. *Desalination* **2014**, 333 (1), 23–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2013.11.014>.
- 974 (16) Cath, T.; Childress, A.; Elimelech, M. Forward Osmosis: Principles, Applications, and Recent
975 Developments. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2006**, 281 (1–2), 70–87.
976 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2006.05.048>.
- 977 (17) Zhao, S.; Zou, L.; Tang, C. Y.; Mulcahy, D. Recent Developments in Forward Osmosis: Opportunities
978 and Challenges. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2012**, 396, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.12.023>.
- 979 (18) Chung, T.-S.; Zhang, S.; Wang, K. Y.; Su, J.; Ling, M. M. Forward Osmosis Processes: Yesterday, Today
980 and Tomorrow. *Desalination* **2012**, 287, 78–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2010.12.019>.

- 981 (19) She, Q.; Wang, R.; Fane, A. G.; Tang, C. Y. Membrane Fouling in Osmotically Driven Membrane
982 Processes: A Review. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2016**, *499*, 201–233.
983 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.10.040>.
- 984 (20) Coday, B. D.; Yaffe, B. G. M.; Xu, P.; Cath, T. Y. Rejection of Trace Organic Compounds by Forward
985 Osmosis Membranes: A Literature Review. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2014**, *48* (7), 3612–3624.
986 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es4038676>.
- 987 (21) Chekli, L.; Phuntsho, S.; Shon, H. K.; Vigneswaran, S.; Kandasamy, J.; Chanan, A. A Review of Draw
988 Solutes in Forward Osmosis Process and Their Use in Modern Applications. *Desalination and Water
989 Treatment* **2012**, *43* (1–3), 167–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2012.672168>.
- 990 (22) Qin, J.-J.; Lay, W. C. L.; Kekre, K. A. Recent Developments and Future Challenges of Forward Osmosis
991 for Desalination: A Review. *Desalination and Water Treatment* **2012**, *15*.
- 992 (23) Shaffer, D. L.; Werber, J. R.; Jaramillo, H.; Lin, S.; Elimelech, M. Forward Osmosis: Where Are We Now?
993 *Desalination* **2015**, *356*, 271–284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.10.031>.
- 994 (24) Shaffer, D. L.; Yip, N. Y.; Gilron, J.; Elimelech, M. Seawater Desalination for Agriculture by Integrated
995 Forward and Reverse Osmosis: Improved Product Water Quality for Potentially Less Energy. *Journal of
996 Membrane Science* **2012**, *415–416*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2012.05.016>.
- 997 (25) Chekli, L.; Phuntsho, S.; Kim, J. E.; Kim, J.; Choi, J. Y.; Choi, J.-S.; Kim, S.; Kim, J. H.; Hong, S.; Sohn, J.;
998 Shon, H. K. A Comprehensive Review of Hybrid Forward Osmosis Systems: Performance, Applications
999 and Future Prospects. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2016**, *497*, 430–449.
1000 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.09.041>.
- 1001 (26) Xie, M.; Nghiem, L. D.; Price, W. E.; Elimelech, M. Toward Resource Recovery from Wastewater:
1002 Extraction of Phosphorus from Digested Sludge Using a Hybrid Forward Osmosis–Membrane
1003 Distillation Process. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters* **2014**, *1* (2), 191–195.
1004 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ez400189z>.
- 1005 (27) Petrotos, K. B.; Lazarides, H. N. Osmotic Concentration of Liquid Foods. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2001**,
1006 *49* (2–3), 201–206. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0260-8774\(00\)00222-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0260-8774(00)00222-3).
- 1007 (28) Sant’Anna, V.; Marczak, L. D. F.; Tessaro, I. C. Membrane Concentration of Liquid Foods by Forward
1008 Osmosis: Process and Quality View. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2012**, *111* (3), 483–489.
1009 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2012.01.032>.
- 1010 (29) Popper, K.; Camirand, W.; Nury, F.; Stanley, W. Dialyzer Concentrates Beverages. *Food Eng* **1966**, *38* (4),
1011 102–104.
- 1012 (30) Beaudry, E.; Lampi, K. Membrane Technology for Direct-Osmosis Concentration of Fruit Juices. *Food
1013 technology (Chicago)* **1990**, *44* (6).
- 1014 (31) Kim, D. I.; Gwak, G.; Zhan, M.; Hong, S. Sustainable Dewatering of Grapefruit Juice through Forward
1015 Osmosis: Improving Membrane Performance, Fouling Control, and Product Quality. *Journal of Membrane
1016 Science* **2019**, *578*, 53–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.02.031>.
- 1017 (32) Sant’Anna, V.; Gurak, P. D.; Vargas, N. S. de; Silva, M. K. da; Marczak, L. D. F.; Tessaro, I. C. Jaboticaba
1018 (Myrciaria Jaboticaba) Juice Concentration by Forward Osmosis. *Separation Science and Technology* **2016**,
1019 *51* (10), 1708–1715. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2016.1168845>.
- 1020 (33) Herron, J. R.; Beaudry, E. G.; Jochums, C. E.; Medina, L. E. Osmotic Concentration Apparatus and
1021 Method for Direct Osmotic Concentration of Fruit Juices. **1994**.

- 1022 (34) Wrolstad, R. E.; Mcdaniel, M. R.; Durst, R. W.; Micheals, N.; Lampi, K. A.; Beaudry, E. G. Composition
1023 and Sensory Characterization of Red Raspberry Juice Concentrated by Direct-Osmosis or Evaporation.
1024 *Journal of Food Science* **1993**, *58* (3), 633–637. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1993.tb04344.x>.
- 1025 (35) Dova, M. I.; Petrotos, K. B.; Lazarides, H. N. On the Direct Osmotic Concentration of Liquid Foods. Part
1026 I: Impact of Process Parameters on Process Performance. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2007**, *78* (2), 422–430.
1027 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2005.10.010>.
- 1028 (36) Petrotos, K. B.; Quantick, P.; Petropakis, H. A Study of the Direct Osmotic Concentration of Tomato Juice
1029 in Tubular Membrane – Module Configuration. I. The Effect of Certain Basic Process Parameters on the
1030 Process Performance. *Journal of Membrane Science* **1998**, *150* (1), 99–110. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388\(98\)00216-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388(98)00216-6).
- 1031
- 1032 (37) Babu, B. R.; Rastogi, N. K.; Raghavarao, K. S. M. S. Effect of Process Parameters on Transmembrane Flux
1033 during Direct Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2006**, *280* (1–2), 185–194.
1034 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2006.01.018>.
- 1035 (38) Nayak, C. A.; Rastogi, N. K. Forward Osmosis for the Concentration of Anthocyanin from *Garcinia*
1036 *Indica* Choisy. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2010**, *71* (2), 144–151.
1037 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2009.11.013>.
- 1038 (39) Nayak, C. A.; Valluri, S. S.; Rastogi, N. K. Effect of High or Low Molecular Weight of Components of
1039 Feed on Transmembrane Flux during Forward Osmosis. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2011**, *106* (1), 48–52.
1040 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2011.04.006>.
- 1041 (40) Valluri, S. Forward Osmosis for Concentration of Liquid Foods. **2010**.
- 1042 (41) Coconut Milk Concentration. *Aquaporin*, 2019.
- 1043 (42) Food & Beverage Solutions <http://www.porifera.com/food-solutions> (accessed Mar 19, 2020).
- 1044 (43) Forward Osmosis for natural flavors/colors - ederna <http://www.ederna.com/beverages> (accessed Mar
1045 19, 2020).
- 1046 (44) An, X.; Hu, Y.; Wang, N.; Zhou, Z.; Liu, Z. Continuous Juice Concentration by Integrating Forward
1047 Osmosis with Membrane Distillation Using Potassium Sorbate Preservative as a Draw Solute. *Journal of*
1048 *Membrane Science* **2019**, *573*, 192–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2018.12.010>.
- 1049 (45) Chanukya, B. S.; Rastogi, N. K. Ultrasound Assisted Forward Osmosis Concentration of Fruit Juice and
1050 Natural Colorant. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry* **2017**, *34*, 426–435.
1051 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2016.06.020>.
- 1052 (46) Petrotos, K. B.; Tsiadi, A. V.; Poirazis, E.; Papadopoulos, D.; Petropakis, H.; Gkoutisidis, P. A Description
1053 of a Flat Geometry Direct Osmotic Concentrator to Concentrate Tomato Juice at Ambient Temperature
1054 and Low Pressure. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2010**, *97* (2), 235–242.
1055 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2009.10.015>.
- 1056 (47) Garcia-Castello, E. M.; McCutcheon, J. R.; Elimelech, M. Performance Evaluation of Sucrose
1057 Concentration Using Forward Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2009**, *338* (1–2), 61–66.
1058 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2009.04.011>.
- 1059 (48) Garcia-Castello, E. M.; McCutcheon, J. R. Dewatering Press Liquor Derived from Orange Production by
1060 Forward Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2011**, *372* (1), 97–101.
1061 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.01.048>.
- 1062 (49) Hasanoğlu, A.; Gül, K. CONCENTRATION OF SKIM MILK AND DAIRY PRODUCTS BY FORWARD
1063 OSMOSIS. *Journal of the Turkish Chemical Society Section B: Chemical Engineering* **2017**, *1* (1), 149–160.

- 1064 (50) Schuck, P.; Jeantet, R.; Tanguy, G.; Méjean, S.; Gac, A.; Lefebvre, T.; Labussière, E.; Martineau, C. Energy
1065 Consumption in the Processing of Dairy and Feed Powders by Evaporation and Drying. *Drying*
1066 *Technology* **2015**, *33* (2), 176–184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07373937.2014.942913>.
- 1067 (51) Burke, N.; Zacharski, K. A.; Southern, M.; Hogan, P.; Ryan, M. P.; Adley, C. C. The Dairy Industry:
1068 Process, Monitoring, Standards, and Quality. *Descriptive Food Science* **2018**.
1069 <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.80398>.
- 1070 (52) Písecký, J. *Handbook of Milk Powder Manufacture*; GEA Process Engineering A/S, 2012.
- 1071 (53) Ramírez, C. A.; Patel, M.; Blok, K. From Fluid Milk to Milk Powder: Energy Use and Energy Efficiency
1072 in the European Dairy Industry. *Energy* **2006**, *31* (12), 1984–2004.
1073 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2005.10.014>.
- 1074 (54) Gea-Membrane-Filtration-Brochure-for-Dairy-Industry_tcm11-17109.Pdf.
- 1075 (55) Chen, G. Q.; Artemi, A.; Lee, J.; Gras, S. L.; Kentish, S. E. A Pilot Scale Study on the Concentration of
1076 Milk and Whey by Forward Osmosis. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2019**, *215*, 652–659.
1077 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.01.050>.
- 1078 (56) Aydiner, C.; Topcu, S.; Tortop, C.; Kuvvet, F.; Ekinçi, D.; Dizge, N.; Keskinler, B. A Novel
1079 Implementation of Water Recovery from Whey: “Forward–Reverse Osmosis” Integrated Membrane
1080 System. *Desalination and Water Treatment* **2013**, *51* (4–6), 786–799.
1081 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2012.693713>.
- 1082 (57) Aydiner, C.; Sen, U.; Topcu, S.; Sesli, D.; Ekinçi, D.; Altınay, A. D.; Ozbey, B.; Koseoglu-Imer, D. Y.;
1083 Keskinler, B. Techno-Economic Investigation of Water Recovery and Whey Powder Production from
1084 Whey Using UF/RO and FO/RO Integrated Membrane Systems. *Desalination and Water Treatment* **2013**,
1085 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2013.786655>.
- 1086 (58) Aydiner, C.; Sen, U.; Topcu, S.; Ekinçi, D.; Altınay, A. D.; Koseoglu-Imer, D. Y.; Keskinler, B. Techno-
1087 Economic Viability of Innovative Membrane Systems in Water and Mass Recovery from Dairy
1088 Wastewater. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, *458*, 66–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.01.058>.
- 1089 (59) Wang, Y.-N.; Wang, R.; Li, W.; Tang, C. Y. Whey Recovery Using Forward Osmosis – Evaluating the
1090 Factors Limiting the Flux Performance. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2017**, *533*, 179–189.
1091 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.03.047>.
- 1092 (60) Schrier, J. Ethanol Concentration by Forward Osmosis with Solar-Regenerated Draw Solution. *Solar*
1093 *Energy* **2012**, *86* (5), 1351–1358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2012.01.027>.
- 1094 (61) Zhang, X.; Ning, Z.; Wang, D. K.; Diniz da Costa, J. C. A Novel Ethanol Dehydration Process by Forward
1095 Osmosis. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2013**, *232*, 397–404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2013.07.106>.
- 1096 (62) Ambrosi, A.; Corrêa, G. L.; Vargas, N. S. de; Gabe, L. M.; Cardozo, N. S. M.; Tessaro, I. C. Impact of
1097 Osmotic Agent on the Transport of Components Using Forward Osmosis to Separate Ethanol from
1098 Aqueous Solutions. *AIChE Journal* **2017**, *63* (10), 4499–4507. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.15779>.
- 1099 (63) Ambrosi, A.; Al-Furaiji, M.; McCutcheon, J. R.; Cardozo, N. S. M.; Tessaro, I. C. Transport of Components
1100 in the Separation of Ethanol from Aqueous Dilute Solutions by Forward Osmosis. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*
1101 **2018**, *57* (8), 2967–2975. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.7b04944>.
- 1102 (64) Nazir, A.; Khan, K.; Maan, A.; Zia, R.; Giorno, L.; Schroën, K. Membrane Separation Technology for the
1103 Recovery of Nutraceuticals from Food Industrial Streams. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **2019**, *86*,
1104 426–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2019.02.049>.

- 1105 (65) Wang, K. Y.; Teoh, M. M.; Nugroho, A.; Chung, T.-S. Integrated Forward Osmosis–Membrane
1106 Distillation (FO–MD) Hybrid System for the Concentration of Protein Solutions. *Chemical Engineering*
1107 *Science* **2011**, *66* (11), 2421–2430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2011.03.001>.
- 1108 (66) Wang, J.; Martínez-Hernández, A.; de Lamo-Castellví, S.; Romero, M.-P.; Kaade, W.; Ferrando, M.; Güell,
1109 C. Low-Energy Membrane-Based Processes to Concentrate and Encapsulate Polyphenols from Carob
1110 Pulp. *Journal of Food Engineering* **2020**, 109996. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2020.109996>.
- 1111 (67) Khongnakorn, W.; Youravong, W. Concentration and Recovery of Protein from Tuna Cooking Juice by
1112 Forward Osmosis. *J. Eng. Sci. Technol.* **2016**, *11*, 962–973.
- 1113 (68) Gebreyohannes, A. Y.; Curcio, E.; Poerio, T.; Mazzei, R.; Di Profio, G.; Drioli, E.; Giorno, L. Treatment of
1114 Olive Mill Wastewater by Forward Osmosis. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2015**, *147*, 292–302.
1115 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2015.04.021>.
- 1116 (69) Singh, N.; Petrinic, I.; Hélix-Nielsen, C.; Basu, S.; Balakrishnan, M. Concentrating Molasses Distillery
1117 Wastewater Using Biomimetic Forward Osmosis (FO) Membranes. *Water Research* **2018**, *130*, 271–280.
1118 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.12.006>.
- 1119 (70) Kim, D. I.; Choi, J.; Hong, S. Evaluation on Suitability of Osmotic Dewatering through Forward Osmosis
1120 (FO) for Xylose Concentration. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2018**, *191*, 225–232.
1121 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2017.09.036>.
- 1122 (71) Mondal, D.; Nataraj, S. K.; Reddy, A. V. R.; Ghara, K. K.; Maiti, P.; Upadhyay, S. C.; Ghosh, P. K. Four-
1123 Fold Concentration of Sucrose in Sugarcane Juice through Energy Efficient Forward Osmosis Using Sea
1124 Bittern as Draw Solution. *RSC Adv.* **2015**, *5* (23), 17872–17878. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA00617A>.
- 1125 (72) Zhang, Y.; Nakagawa, K.; Shibuya, M.; Sasaki, K.; Takahashi, T.; Shintani, T.; Yoshioka, T.; Kamio, E.;
1126 Kondo, A.; Matsuyama, H. Improved Permselectivity of Forward Osmosis Membranes for Efficient
1127 Concentration of Pretreated Rice Straw and Bioethanol Production. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2018**, *566*,
1128 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2018.08.046>.
- 1129 (73) Shibuya, M.; Yasukawa, M.; Sasaki, K.; Tanaka, Y.; Takahashi, T.; Kondo, A.; Matsuyama, H. Up-
1130 Concentration of Sugars in Pretreated-Rice Straw by an Osmotic Pressure-Driven Method. *Biochemical*
1131 *Engineering Journal* **2017**, *121*, 13–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2017.01.012>.
- 1132 (74) Garcia-Aguirre, J.; Alvarado-Morales, M.; Fotidis, I. A.; Angelidaki, I. Up-Concentration of Succinic
1133 Acid, Lactic Acid, and Ethanol Fermentations Broths by Forward Osmosis. *Biochemical Engineering*
1134 *Journal* **2020**, *155*, 107482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2019.107482>.
- 1135 (75) Blandin, G.; Rosselló, B.; Monsalvo, V. M.; Batlle-Vilanova, P.; Viñas, J. M.; Rogalla, F.; Comas, J. Volatile
1136 Fatty Acids Concentration in Real Wastewater by Forward Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2019**,
1137 *575*, 60–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.01.006>.
- 1138 (76) Cui, Y.; Chung, T.-S. Pharmaceutical Concentration Using Organic Solvent Forward Osmosis for Solvent
1139 Recovery. *Nat Commun* **2018**, *9* (1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03612-2>.
- 1140 (77) Singh, N.; Petrinic, I.; Hélix-Nielsen, C.; Basu, S.; Balakrishnan, M. Influence of Forward Osmosis (FO)
1141 Membrane Properties on Dewatering of Molasses Distillery Wastewater. *Journal of Water Process*
1142 *Engineering* **2019**, *32*, 100921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2019.100921>.
- 1143 (78) Draaisma, R. B.; Wijffels, R. H.; (Ellen) Slegers, P.; Brentner, L. B.; Roy, A.; Barbosa, M. J. Food
1144 Commodities from Microalgae. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology* **2013**, *24* (2), 169–177.
1145 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copbio.2012.09.012>.
- 1146 (79) Vanthoor-Koopmans, M.; Wijffels, R. H.; Barbosa, M. J.; Eppink, M. H. M. Biorefinery of Microalgae for
1147 Food and Fuel. *Bioresource Technology* **2013**, *135*, 142–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2012.10.135>.

- 1148 (80) Chisti, Y. Biodiesel from Microalgae. *Biotechnology Advances* **2007**, *25* (3), 294–306.
1149 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2007.02.001>.
- 1150 (81) Trent, J.; Embaye, T.; Buckwalter, P.; Richardson, T.-M.; Kagawa, H.; Reinsch, S.; Martis, M. Offshore
1151 Membrane Enclosures for Growing Algae (OMEGA: A System for Biofuel Production, Wastewater
1152 Treatment, and CO₂ Sequestration. **2010**.
- 1153 (82) Delrue, F.; Álvarez-Díaz, P. D.; Fon-Sing, S.; Fleury, G.; Sassi, J.-F. The Environmental Biorefinery: Using
1154 Microalgae to Remediate Wastewater, a Win-Win Paradigm. *Energies* **2016**, *9* (3), 132.
1155 <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9030132>.
- 1156 (83) Bilad, M. R.; Arafat, H. A.; Vankelecom, I. F. J. Membrane Technology in Microalgae Cultivation and
1157 Harvesting: A Review. *Biotechnology Advances* **2014**, *32* (7), 1283–1300.
1158 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2014.07.008>.
- 1159 (84) Udom, I.; Zaribaf, B. H.; Halfhide, T.; Gillie, B.; Dalrymple, O.; Zhang, Q.; Ergas, S. J. Harvesting
1160 Microalgae Grown on Wastewater. *Bioresource Technology* **2013**, *139*, 101–106.
1161 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.04.002>.
- 1162 (85) Wang, J.-H.; Zhang, T.-Y.; Dao, G.-H.; Xu, X.-Q.; Wang, X.-X.; Hu, H.-Y. Microalgae-Based Advanced
1163 Municipal Wastewater Treatment for Reuse in Water Bodies. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* **2017**, *101* (7), 2659–
1164 2675. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-017-8184-x>.
- 1165 (86) Liu, J.; Wu, Y.; Wu, C.; Muylaert, K.; Vyverman, W.; Yu, H.-Q.; Muñoz, R.; Rittmann, B. Advanced
1166 Nutrient Removal from Surface Water by a Consortium of Attached Microalgae and Bacteria: A Review.
1167 *Bioresource Technology* **2017**, *241*, 1127–1137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.06.054>.
- 1168 (87) Wibisono, Y.; Agung Nugroho, W.; Akbar Devianto, L.; Adi Sulianto, A.; Roil Bilad, M. Microalgae in
1169 Food-Energy-Water Nexus: A Review on Progress of Forward Osmosis Applications. *Membranes* **2019**, *9*
1170 (12), 166. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes9120166>.
- 1171 (88) Onyshchenko, E.; Blandin, G.; Comas, J.; Dvoretzky, A. Influence of Microalgae Wastewater Treatment
1172 Culturing Conditions on Forward Osmosis Concentration Process. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* **2018**.
1173 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-3607-5>.
- 1174 (89) Praveen, P.; Heng, J. Y. P.; Loh, K.-C. Tertiary Wastewater Treatment in Membrane Photobioreactor
1175 Using Microalgae: Comparison of Forward Osmosis & Microfiltration. *Bioresource Technology* **2016**, *222*,
1176 448–457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.09.124>.
- 1177 (90) Praveen, P.; Loh, K.-C. Nitrogen and Phosphorus Removal from Tertiary Wastewater in an Osmotic
1178 Membrane Photobioreactor. *Bioresource Technology* **2016**, *206*, 180–187.
1179 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.01.102>.
- 1180 (91) Buckwalter, P.; Embaye, T.; Gormly, S.; Trent, J. D. Dewatering Microalgae by Forward Osmosis.
1181 *Desalination* **2013**, *312*, 19–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2012.12.015>.
- 1182 (92) Ye, J.; Zhou, Q.; Zhang, X.; Hu, Q. Microalgal Dewatering Using a Polyamide Thin Film Composite
1183 Forward Osmosis Membrane and Fouling Mitigation. *Algal Research* **2018**, *31*, 421–429.
1184 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2018.02.003>.
- 1185 (93) Volpin, F.; Yu, H.; Cho, J.; Lee, C.; Phuntsho, S.; Ghaffour, N.; Vrouwenvelder, J. S.; Shon, H. K. Human
1186 Urine as a Forward Osmosis Draw Solution for the Application of Microalgae Dewatering. *Journal of*
1187 *Hazardous Materials* **2019**, *378*, 120724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.06.001>.
- 1188 (94) Mazzuca Sobczuk, T.; Ibáñez González, M. J.; Molina Grima, E.; Chisti, Y. Forward Osmosis with Waste
1189 Glycerol for Concentrating Microalgae Slurries. *Algal Research* **2015**, *8*, 168–173.
1190 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2015.02.008>.

- 1191 (95) Ryu, H.; Kim, K.; Cho, H.; Park, E.; Chang, Y. K.; Han, J.-I. Nutrient-Driven Forward Osmosis Coupled
1192 with Microalgae Cultivation for Energy Efficient Dewatering of Microalgae. *Algal Research* **2020**, *48*,
1193 101880. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2020.101880>.
- 1194 (96) Onyshchenko, E.; Blandin, G.; Comas, J.; Dvoretzky, A. Design and Evaluation of a Forward Osmosis
1195 Microalgae Bioreactor to Combine Microalgae Dewatering and Wastewater Reuse; Barcelona, 2017.
- 1196 (97) Larronde-Larretche, M.; Jin, X. Microalgae (*Scenedesmus Obliquus*) Dewatering Using Forward
1197 Osmosis Membrane: Influence of Draw Solution Chemistry. *Algal Research* **2016**, *15*, 1–8.
1198 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2016.01.014>.
- 1199 (98) Itliong, J. N.; Villagracia, A. R. C.; Moreno, J. L. V.; Rojas, K. I. M.; Bernardo, G. P. O.; David, M. Y.;
1200 Manrique, R. B.; Ubando, A. T.; Culaba, A. B.; Padama, A. A. B.; Ong, H. L.; Chang, J.-S.; Chen, W.-H.;
1201 Kasai, H.; Arboleda, N. B. Investigation of Reverse Ionic Diffusion in Forward-Osmosis-Aided
1202 Dewatering of Microalgae: A Molecular Dynamics Study. *Bioresource Technology* **2019**, *279*, 181–188.
1203 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.01.109>.
- 1204 (99) Honda, R.; Rukapan, W.; Komura, H.; Teraoka, Y.; Noguchi, M.; Hoek, E. M. V. Effects of Membrane
1205 Orientation on Fouling Characteristics of Forward Osmosis Membrane in Concentration of Microalgae
1206 Culture. *Bioresource Technology* **2015**, *197*, 429–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.08.096>.
- 1207 (100) Zou, S.; Gu, Y.; Xiao, D.; Tang, C. Y. The Role of Physical and Chemical Parameters on Forward Osmosis
1208 Membrane Fouling during Algae Separation. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2011**, *366* (1–2), 356–362.
1209 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2010.10.030>.
- 1210 (101) Lee, W. S.; Chua, A. S. M.; Yeoh, H. K.; Ngoh, G. C. A Review of the Production and Applications of
1211 Waste-Derived Volatile Fatty Acids. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2014**, *235*, 83–99.
1212 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2013.09.002>.
- 1213 (102) Cagnetta, C.; D'Haese, A.; Coma, M.; Props, R.; Buyschaert, B.; Verliefe, A. R. D.; Rabaey, K. Increased
1214 Carboxylate Production in High-Rate Activated A-Sludge by Forward Osmosis Thickening. *Chemical*
1215 *Engineering Journal* **2017**, *312*, 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.11.119>.
- 1216 (103) Jung, K.; Choi, J.; Lee, D.; Seo, C.; Lee, J.; Lee, S. Y.; Chang, H. N.; Kim, Y.-C. Permeation Characteristics
1217 of Volatile Fatty Acids Solution by Forward Osmosis. *Process Biochemistry* **2015**, *50* (4), 669–677.
1218 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2015.01.016>.
- 1219 (104) Lutchmiah, K.; Cornelissen, E. R.; Harmsen, D. J. H.; Post, J. W.; Lampi, K.; Ramaekers, H.; Rietveld, L.
1220 C.; Roest, K. Water Recovery from Sewage Using Forward Osmosis. *Water Science and Technology* **2011**,
1221 *64* (7), 1443–1449. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2011.773>.
- 1222 (105) Phuntsho, S.; Shon, H. K.; Hong, S.; Lee, S.; Vigneswaran, S. A Novel Low Energy Fertilizer Driven
1223 Forward Osmosis Desalination for Direct Fertigation: Evaluating the Performance of Fertilizer Draw
1224 Solutions. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2011**, *375* (1–2), 172–181.
1225 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.03.038>.
- 1226 (106) Valladares Linares, R.; Li, Z.; Abu-Ghdaib, M.; Wei, C. H.; Amy, G.; Vrouwenvelder, J. S. Water
1227 Harvesting from Municipal Wastewater via Osmotic Gradient: An Evaluation of Process Performance.
1228 *Journal of Membrane Science* **2013**, *447*, 50–56.
- 1229 (107) Lee, S.; Boo, C.; Elimelech, M.; Hong, S. Comparison of Fouling Behavior in Forward Osmosis (FO) and
1230 Reverse Osmosis (RO). *Journal of Membrane Science* **2010**, *365* (1–2), 34–39.
1231 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2010.08.036>.

- 1232 (108) Cath, T. Y.; Hancock, N. T.; Lundin, C. D.; Hoppe-Jones, C.; Drewes, J. E. A Multi-Barrier Osmotic
1233 Dilution Process for Simultaneous Desalination and Purification of Impaired Water. *Journal of Membrane*
1234 *Science* **2010**, *362* (1–2), 417–426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2010.06.056>.
- 1235 (109) Hancock, N. T.; Black, N. D.; Cath, T. Y. A Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Hybrid Osmotic
1236 Dilution Desalination and Established Seawater Desalination and Wastewater Reclamation Processes.
1237 *Water Research* **2012**, *46* (4), 1145–1154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2011.12.004>.
- 1238 (110) Blandin, G.; Verliefde, A.; Comas, J.; Rodriguez-Roda, I.; Le-Clech, P. Efficiently Combining Water Reuse
1239 and Desalination through Forward Osmosis–Reverse Osmosis (FO-RO) Hybrids: A Critical Review.
1240 *Membranes* **2016**, *6* (3), 37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes6030037>.
- 1241 (111) Blandin, G.; Verliefde, A. R. D.; Tang, C. Y.; Le-Clech, P. Opportunities to Reach Economic Sustainability
1242 in Forward Osmosis–Reverse Osmosis Hybrids for Seawater Desalination. *Desalination* **2015**, *363*, 26–36.
1243 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.12.011>.
- 1244 (112) Teusner, A.; Blandin, G.; Le-Clech, P. Augmenting Water Supply by Combined Desalination/Water
1245 Recycling Methods: An Economic Assessment. *Environmental Technology* **2017**, *38* (3), 257–265.
1246 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2016.1189972>.
- 1247 (113) Large Scale FO-Based Desalination | ForwardOsmosisTech.
- 1248 (114) Holloway, R.; Childress, A.; Dennett, K.; Cath, T. Forward Osmosis for Concentration of Anaerobic
1249 Digester Centrate. *Water Research* **2007**, *41* (17), 4005–4014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.05.054>.
- 1250 (115) Nguyen, N. C.; Chen, S.-S.; Yang, H.-Y.; Hau, N. T. Application of Forward Osmosis on Dewatering of
1251 High Nutrient Sludge. *Bioresour Technol* **2013**, *132*, 224–229.
1252 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.01.028>.
- 1253 (116) Butler, R.; MacCormick, T. Opportunities for Decentralized Treatment, Sewer Mining and Effluent Re-
1254 Use. *Desalination* **1996**, *106* (1–3), 273–283. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0011-9164\(96\)00119-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0011-9164(96)00119-1).
- 1255 (117) Ansari, A. J.; Hai, F. I.; Price, W. E.; Ngo, H. H.; Guo, W.; Nghiem, L. D. Assessing the Integration of
1256 Forward Osmosis and Anaerobic Digestion for Simultaneous Wastewater Treatment and Resource
1257 Recovery. *Bioresour Technol* **2018**, *260*, 221–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.03.120>.
- 1258 (118) Ansari, A. J.; Hai, F. I.; Price, W. E.; Drewes, J. E.; Nghiem, L. D. Forward Osmosis as a Platform for
1259 Resource Recovery from Municipal Wastewater - A Critical Assessment of the Literature. *Journal of*
1260 *Membrane Science* **2017**, *529*, 195–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.01.054>.
- 1261 (119) Zhang, X.; Ning, Z.; Wang, D. K.; Diniz da Costa, J. C. Processing Municipal Wastewaters by Forward
1262 Osmosis Using CTA Membrane. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, *468*, 269–275.
1263 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.06.016>.
- 1264 (120) Ansari, A. J.; Hai, F. I.; Guo, W.; Ngo, H. H.; Price, W. E.; Nghiem, L. D. Factors Governing the Pre-
1265 Concentration of Wastewater Using Forward Osmosis for Subsequent Resource Recovery. *Science of The*
1266 *Total Environment* **2016**, *566–567*, 559–566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.05.139>.
- 1267 (121) Ferrari, F.; Pijuan, M.; Rodriguez-Roda, I.; Blandin, G. Exploring Submerged Forward Osmosis for Water
1268 Recovery and Pre-Concentration of Wastewater before Anaerobic Digestion: A Pilot Scale Study.
1269 *Membranes* **2019**, *9* (8), 97. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes9080097>.
- 1270 (122) Wang, Z.; Zheng, J.; Tang, J.; Wang, X.; Wu, Z. A Pilot-Scale Forward Osmosis Membrane System for
1271 Concentrating Low-Strength Municipal Wastewater: Performance and Implications. *Sci Rep* **2016**, *6* (1),
1272 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep21653>.
- 1273 (123) Bao, X.; Wu, Q.; Tian, J.; Shi, W.; Wang, W.; Zhang, Z.; Zhang, R.; Zhang, B.; Guo, Y.; Shu, S.; Cui, F.
1274 Fouling Mechanism of Forward Osmosis Membrane in Domestic Wastewater Concentration: Role of

- 1275 Substrate Structures. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2019**, *370*, 262–273.
1276 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.03.174>.
- 1277 (124) Cornelissen, E. R.; Harmsen, D.; Beerendonk, E. F.; Qin, J. J.; Oo, H.; de Korte, K. F.; Kappelhof, J. W. M.
1278 N. The Innovative Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor (OMBR) for Reuse of Wastewater. *Water Science and*
1279 *Technology* **2011**, *63* (8), 1557–1565. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2011.206>.
- 1280 (125) Holloway, R. W.; Achilli, A.; Cath, T. Y. The Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor: A Critical Review. *Environ.*
1281 *Sci.: Water Res. Technol.* **2015**, *1* (5), 581–605. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5EW00103J>.
- 1282 (126) Blandin, G.; Le-Clech, P.; Cornelissen, E.; Verliefde, A. R. D.; Comas, J.; Rodriguez-Roda, I. Can Osmotic
1283 Membrane Bioreactor Be a Realistic Solution for Water Reuse? *npj Clean Water* **2018**, *1* (1), 7.
1284 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-018-0006-x>.
- 1285 (127) Blandin, G.; Gautier, C.; Sauchelli Toran, M.; Monclús, H.; Rodriguez-Roda, I.; Comas, J. Retrofitting
1286 Membrane Bioreactor (MBR) into Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor (OMBR): A Pilot Scale Study. *Chemical*
1287 *Engineering Journal* **2018**, *339*, 268–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.01.103>.
- 1288 (128) Luo, W.; Phan, H. V.; Xie, M.; Hai, F. I.; Price, W. E.; Elimelech, M.; Nghiem, L. D. Osmotic versus
1289 Conventional Membrane Bioreactors Integrated with Reverse Osmosis for Water Reuse: Biological
1290 Stability, Membrane Fouling, and Contaminant Removal. *Water Research* **2017**, *109*, 122–134.
1291 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.11.036>.
- 1292 (129) Wang, X.; Chang, V. W. C.; Tang, C. Y. Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor (OMBR) Technology for
1293 Wastewater Treatment and Reclamation: Advances, Challenges, and Prospects for the Future. *Journal of*
1294 *Membrane Science* **2016**, *504*, 113–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2016.01.010>.
- 1295 (130) Holloway, R. W.; Wait, A. S.; Fernandes da Silva, A.; Herron, J.; Schutter, M. D.; Lampi, K.; Cath, T. Y.
1296 Long-Term Pilot Scale Investigation of Novel Hybrid Ultrafiltration-Osmotic Membrane Bioreactors.
1297 *Desalination* **2015**, *363*, 64–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.05.040>.
- 1298 (131) Luo, W.; Hai, F. I.; Kang, J.; Price, W. E.; Nghiem, L. D.; Elimelech, M. The Role of Forward Osmosis and
1299 Microfiltration in an Integrated Osmotic-Microfiltration Membrane Bioreactor System. *Chemosphere* **2015**,
1300 *136*, 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.04.082>.
- 1301 (132) Qiu, G.; Ting, Y.-P. Direct Phosphorus Recovery from Municipal Wastewater via Osmotic Membrane
1302 Bioreactor (OMBR) for Wastewater Treatment. *Bioresource Technology* **2014**, *170*, 221–229.
1303 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2014.07.103>.
- 1304 (133) Qiu, G.; Zhang, S.; Srinivasa Raghavan, D. S.; Das, S.; Ting, Y.-P. The Potential of Hybrid Forward
1305 Osmosis Membrane Bioreactor (FOMBR) Processes in Achieving High Throughput Treatment of
1306 Municipal Wastewater with Enhanced Phosphorus Recovery. *Water Research* **2016**, *105*, 370–382.
1307 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.09.017>.
- 1308 (134) Xue, W.; Tobino, T.; Nakajima, F.; Yamamoto, K. Seawater-Driven Forward Osmosis for Enriching
1309 Nitrogen and Phosphorous in Treated Municipal Wastewater: Effect of Membrane Properties and Feed
1310 Solution Chemistry. *Water Research* **2015**, *69*, 120–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2014.11.007>.
- 1311 (135) Xue, W.; Yamamoto, K.; Tobino, T. Membrane Fouling and Long-Term Performance of Seawater-Driven
1312 Forward Osmosis for Enrichment of Nutrients in Treated Municipal Wastewater. *Journal of Membrane*
1313 *Science* **2016**, *499*, 555–562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.11.009>.
- 1314 (136) Giménez, J. B.; Robles, A.; Carretero, L.; Durán, F.; Ruano, M. V.; Gatti, M. N.; Ribes, J.; Ferrer, J.; Seco,
1315 A. Experimental Study of the Anaerobic Urban Wastewater Treatment in a Submerged Hollow-Fibre
1316 Membrane Bioreactor at Pilot Scale. *Bioresource Technology* **2011**, *102* (19), 8799–8806.
1317 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.07.014>.

- 1318 (137) Pretel, R.; Robles, A.; Ruano, M. V.; Seco, A.; Ferrer, J. The Operating Cost of an Anaerobic Membrane
1319 Bioreactor (AnMBR) Treating Sulphate-Rich Urban Wastewater. *Separation and Purification Technology*
1320 **2014**, *126*, 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2014.02.013>.
- 1321 (138) Chen, L.; Gu, Y.; Cao, C.; Zhang, J.; Ng, J.-W.; Tang, C. Performance of a Submerged Anaerobic
1322 Membrane Bioreactor with Forward Osmosis Membrane for Low-Strength Wastewater Treatment. *Water*
1323 *Research* **2014**, *50*, 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2013.12.009>.
- 1324 (139) Gu, Y.; Chen, L.; Ng, J.-W.; Lee, C.; Chang, V. W.-C.; Tang, C. Y. Development of Anaerobic Osmotic
1325 Membrane Bioreactor for Low-Strength Wastewater Treatment at Mesophilic Condition. *Journal of*
1326 *Membrane Science* **2015**, *490*, 197–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.04.032>.
- 1327 (140) Tang, M. K. Y.; Ng, H. Y. Impacts of Different Draw Solutions on a Novel Anaerobic Forward Osmosis
1328 Membrane Bioreactor (AnFOMBR). *Water Sci Technol* **2014**, *69* (10), 2036–2042.
1329 <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2014.116>.
- 1330 (141) Wang, X.; Wang, C.; Tang, C. Y.; Hu, T.; Li, X.; Ren, Y. Development of a Novel Anaerobic Membrane
1331 Bioreactor Simultaneously Integrating Microfiltration and Forward Osmosis Membranes for Low-
1332 Strength Wastewater Treatment. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2017**, *527*, 1–7.
1333 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2016.12.062>.
- 1334 (142) Vinardell, S.; Astals, S.; Mata-Alvarez, J.; Dosta, J. Techno-Economic Analysis of Combining Forward
1335 Osmosis-Reverse Osmosis and Anaerobic Membrane Bioreactor Technologies for Municipal Wastewater
1336 Treatment and Water Production. *Bioresource Technology* **2020**, *297*, 122395.
1337 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.122395>.
- 1338 (143) Wang, X.; Zhao, Y.; Yuan, B.; Wang, Z.; Li, X.; Ren, Y. Comparison of Biofouling Mechanisms between
1339 Cellulose Triacetate (CTA) and Thin-Film Composite (TFC) Polyamide Forward Osmosis Membranes in
1340 Osmotic Membrane Bioreactors. *Bioresource Technology* **2016**, *202*, 50–58.
1341 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.11.087>.
- 1342 (144) Holloway, R. W.; Regnery, J.; Nghiem, L. D.; Cath, T. Y. Removal of Trace Organic Chemicals and
1343 Performance of a Novel Hybrid Ultrafiltration-Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor. *Environmental Science and*
1344 *Technology* **2014**, *48* (18), 10859–10868. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es501051b>.
- 1345 (145) Qiu, G.; Law, Y.; Das, S.; Ting, Y. Direct and Complete Phosphorus Recovery from Municipal
1346 Wastewater Using a Hybrid Micro Filtration-Forward Osmosis Membrane Bioreactor Process with
1347 Seawater Brine as Draw Solution. **2015**. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es504554f>.
- 1348 (146) Qiu, G.; Ting, Y. P. Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor for Wastewater Treatment and the Effect of Salt
1349 Accumulation on System Performance and Microbial Community Dynamics. *Bioresource Technology*
1350 **2013**, *150*, 287–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.09.090>.
- 1351 (147) Sun, Y.; Tian, J.; Song, L.; Gao, S.; Shi, W.; Cui, F. Dynamic Changes of the Fouling Layer in Forward
1352 Osmosis Based Membrane Processes for Municipal Wastewater Treatment. *Journal of Membrane Science*
1353 **2018**, *549* (November 2017), 523–532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.12.055>.
- 1354 (148) Chang, H. M.; Sun, Y. C.; Chien, I. C.; Chang, W. S.; Ray, S. S.; Cao, D. T. N.; Cong Duong, C.; Chen, S. S.
1355 Innovative Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Osmotic Membrane Bioreactor for Wastewater Treatment.
1356 *Bioresource Technology* **2019**, *287* (May), 121466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.121466>.
- 1357 (149) Yang, S.; Gao, B.; Jang, A.; Shon, H. kyong; Yue, Q. Municipal Wastewater Treatment by Forward
1358 Osmosis Using Seawater Concentrate as Draw Solution. *Chemosphere* **2019**, *237*.
1359 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.124485>.

- 1360 (150) Gao, Y.; Fang, Z.; Liang, P.; Huang, X. Direct Concentration of Municipal Sewage by Forward Osmosis
1361 and Membrane Fouling Behavior. *Bioresource Technology* **2017**.
1362 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.09.145>.
- 1363 (151) Singh, N.; Dhiman, S.; Basu, S.; Balakrishnan, M.; Petrinic, I.; Helix-Nielsen, C. Dewatering of Sewage
1364 for Nutrients and Water Recovery by Forward Osmosis (FO) Using Divalent Draw Solution. *Journal of*
1365 *Water Process Engineering* **2019**, *31* (May), 100853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2019.100853>.
- 1366 (152) Song, Y.-C.; Kim, M.; Shon, H.; Jegatheesan, V.; Kim, S. Modeling Methane Production in Anaerobic
1367 Forward Osmosis Bioreactor Using a Modified Anaerobic Digestion Model No. 1. *Bioresource Technology*
1368 **2018**, *264*, 211–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.04.125>.
- 1369 (153) Li, J.; Hou, D.; Li, K.; Zhang, Y.; Wang, J.; Zhang, X. Domestic Wastewater Treatment by Forward
1370 Osmosis-Membrane Distillation (FO-MD) Integrated System. *Water Sci Technol* **2018**, *77* (6), 1514–1523.
1371 <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2018.031>.
- 1372 (154) Sun, Y.; Tian, J.; Zhao, Z.; Shi, W.; Liu, D.; Cui, F. Membrane Fouling of Forward Osmosis (FO)
1373 Membrane for Municipal Wastewater Treatment: A Comparison between Direct FO and OMBR. *Water*
1374 *Research* **2016**, *104*, 330–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.08.039>.
- 1375 (155) Zhu, H.; Zhang, L.; Wen, X.; Huang, X. Feasibility of Applying Forward Osmosis to the Simultaneous
1376 Thickening, Digestion, and Direct Dewatering of Waste Activated Sludge. *Bioresource Technology* **2012**,
1377 *113*, 207–213. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.12.064>.
- 1378 (156) Nguyen, N. C.; Nguyen, H. T.; Ho, S.-T.; Chen, S.-S.; Ngo, H. H.; Guo, W.; Ray, S. S.; Hsu, H.-T. Exploring
1379 High Charge of Phosphate as New Draw Solute in a Forward Osmosis–Membrane Distillation Hybrid
1380 System for Concentrating High-Nutrient Sludge. *Science of The Total Environment* **2016**, *557–558*, 44–50.
1381 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.03.025>.
- 1382 (157) Hau, N. T.; Chen, S.-S.; Nguyen, N. C.; Huang, K. Z.; Ngo, H. H.; Guo, W. Exploration of EDTA Sodium
1383 Salt as Novel Draw Solution in Forward Osmosis Process for Dewatering of High Nutrient Sludge.
1384 *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, *455*, 305–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.12.068>.
- 1385 (158) Lee, S.; Shon, H. K.; Hong, S. Dewatering of Activated Sludge by Forward Osmosis (FO) with Ultrasound
1386 for Fouling Control. *Desalination* **2017**, *421*, 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2017.02.010>.
- 1387 (159) Nguyen, N. C.; Nguyen, H. T.; Chen, S.-S.; Nguyen, N. T.; Li, C.-W. Application of Forward Osmosis
1388 (FO) under Ultrasonication on Sludge Thickening of Waste Activated Sludge. *Water Sci Technol* **2015**, *72*
1389 (8), 1301–1307. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2015.341>.
- 1390 (160) Larsen*, T. A.; Alder, A. C.; Eggen, R. I. L.; Maurer, M.; Lienert, J. Source Separation: Will We See a
1391 Paradigm Shift in Wastewater Handling? *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2009**, *43* (16), 6121–6125.
1392 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es803001r>.
- 1393 (161) Zhang, J.; She, Q.; Chang, V. W. C.; Tang, C. Y.; Webster, R. D. Mining Nutrients (N, K, P) from Urban
1394 Source-Separated Urine by Forward Osmosis Dewatering. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2014**, *48* (6), 3386–3394.
1395 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es405266d>.
- 1396 (162) Volpin, F.; Chekli, L.; Phuntsho, S.; Cho, J.; Ghaffour, N.; Vrouwenvelder, J. S.; Kyong Shon, H.
1397 Simultaneous Phosphorous and Nitrogen Recovery from Source-Separated Urine: A Novel Application
1398 for Fertiliser Drawn Forward Osmosis. *Chemosphere* **2018**, *203*, 482–489.
1399 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.03.193>.
- 1400 (163) Maurer, M.; Pronk, W.; Larsen, T. A. Treatment Processes for Source-Separated Urine. *Water Research*
1401 **2006**, *40* (17), 3151–3166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2006.07.012>.

- 1402 (164) Nikiema, B. C. W.-Y.; Ito, R.; Guizani, M.; Funamizu, N. Estimation of Water Flux and Solute Movement
1403 during the Concentration Process of Hydrolysed Urine by Forward Osmosis. *Journal of Water and*
1404 *Environment Technology* **2017**, *15* (5), 163–173. <https://doi.org/10.2965/jwet.16-074>.
- 1405 (165) Xu, Y.; Zhou, L.; Jia, Q. Nutrients Recovery of Source-Separated Urine by Forward Osmosis and a Pilot-
1406 Scale Resources-Oriented Sanitation System. *Desalin. Water Treat* **2017**, *91*, 252–259.
- 1407 (166) Volpin, F.; Chekli, L.; Phuntsho, S.; Ghaffour, N.; Vrouwenvelder, J. S.; Shon, H. K. Optimisation of a
1408 Forward Osmosis and Membrane Distillation Hybrid System for the Treatment of Source-Separated
1409 Urine. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2019**, *212*, 368–375.
1410 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2018.11.003>.
- 1411 (167) Ray, H.; Perreault, F.; Boyer, T. H. Urea Recovery from Fresh Human Urine by Forward Osmosis and
1412 Membrane Distillation (FO–MD). *Environ. Sci.: Water Res. Technol.* **2019**, *5* (11), 1993–2003.
1413 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EW00720B>.
- 1414 (168) Liu, Q.; Liu, C.; Zhao, L.; Ma, W.; Liu, H.; Ma, J. Integrated Forward Osmosis-Membrane Distillation
1415 Process for Human Urine Treatment. *Water Research* **2016**, *91*, 45–54.
1416 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2015.12.045>.
- 1417 (169) Volpin, F.; Heo, H.; Hasan Johir, M. A.; Cho, J.; Phuntsho, S.; Shon, H. K. Techno-Economic Feasibility
1418 of Recovering Phosphorus, Nitrogen and Water from Dilute Human Urine via Forward Osmosis. *Water*
1419 *Research* **2019**, *150*, 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.11.056>.
- 1420 (170) Renou, S.; Givaudan, J. G.; Poulain, S.; Dirassouyan, F.; Moulin, P. Landfill Leachate Treatment: Review
1421 and Opportunity. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* **2008**, *150* (3), 468–493.
1422 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.09.077>.
- 1423 (171) LIFE LEACHLESS <https://lifeleachless.eu/en/> (accessed Jun 3, 2020).
- 1424 (172) Lampi, K.; Shethji, J. Forward Osmosis Industrial Wastewater Treatment: Landfill Leachate and Oil and
1425 Gas Produced Waters. *International Forward Osmosis Association World Summit* **2014**.
- 1426 (173) Iskander, S. M.; Novak, J. T.; He, Z. Reduction of Reagent Requirements and Sludge Generation in
1427 Fenton's Oxidation of Landfill Leachate by Synergistically Incorporating Forward Osmosis and Humic
1428 Acid Recovery. *Water Research* **2019**, *151*, 310–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.11.089>.
- 1429 (174) Wu, S.; Zou, S.; Liang, G.; Qian, G.; He, Z. Enhancing Recovery of Magnesium as Struvite from Landfill
1430 Leachate by Pretreatment of Calcium with Simultaneous Reduction of Liquid Volume via Forward
1431 Osmosis. *Science of The Total Environment* **2018**, *610–611*, 137–146.
1432 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.08.038>.
- 1433 (175) Iskander, S. M.; Novak, J. T.; He, Z. Enhancing Forward Osmosis Water Recovery from Landfill Leachate
1434 by Desalinating Brine and Recovering Ammonia in a Microbial Desalination Cell. *Bioresource Technology*
1435 **2018**, *255*, 76–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.01.097>.
- 1436 (176) Qin, M.; Molitor, H.; Brazil, B.; Novak, J. T.; He, Z. Recovery of Nitrogen and Water from Landfill
1437 Leachate by a Microbial Electrolysis Cell–Forward Osmosis System. *Bioresource Technology* **2016**, *200*,
1438 485–492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.10.066>.
- 1439 (177) Dong, Y.; Wang, Z.; Zhu, C.; Wang, Q.; Tang, J.; Wu, Z. A Forward Osmosis Membrane System for the
1440 Post-Treatment of MBR-Treated Landfill Leachate. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, *471*, 192–200.
1441 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.08.023>.
- 1442 (178) Li, J.; Niu, A.; Lu, C.-J.; Zhang, J.-H.; Junaid, M.; Strauss, P. R.; Xiao, P.; Wang, X.; Ren, Y.-W.; Pei, D.-S.
1443 A Novel Forward Osmosis System in Landfill Leachate Treatment for Removing Polycyclic Aromatic

- 1444 Hydrocarbons and for Direct Fertigation. *Chemosphere* **2017**, *168*, 112–121.
1445 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2016.10.048>.
- 1446 (179) Zhou, Y.; Huang, M.; Deng, Q.; Cai, T. Combination and Performance of Forward Osmosis and
1447 Membrane Distillation (FO-MD) for Treatment of High Salinity Landfill Leachate. *Desalination* **2017**, *420*,
1448 99–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2017.06.027>.
- 1449 (180) Shi, L.; Simplicio, W. S.; Wu, G.; Hu, Z.; Hu, H.; Zhan, X. Nutrient Recovery from Digestate of Anaerobic
1450 Digestion of Livestock Manure: A Review. *Curr Pollution Rep* **2018**, *4* (2), 74–83.
1451 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40726-018-0082-z>.
- 1452 (181) Logan, M.; Visvanathan, C. Management Strategies for Anaerobic Digestate of Organic Fraction of
1453 Municipal Solid Waste: Current Status and Future Prospects. *Waste Manag Res* **2019**, *37* (1_suppl), 27–39.
1454 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X18816793>.
- 1455 (182) Schneider, C.; Rajmohan, R. S.; Zarebska, A.; Tsapekos, P.; Hélix-Nielsen, C. Treating Anaerobic
1456 Effluents Using Forward Osmosis for Combined Water Purification and Biogas Production. *Science of*
1457 *The Total Environment* **2019**, *647*, 1021–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.036>.
- 1458 (183) Camilleri-Rumbau, M. S.; Soler-Cabezas, J. L.; Christensen, K. V.; Norddahl, B.; Mendoza-Roca, J. A.;
1459 Vincent-Vela, M. C. Application of Aquaporin-Based Forward Osmosis Membranes for Processing of
1460 Digestate Liquid Fractions. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2019**, *371*, 583–592.
1461 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.02.029>.
- 1462 (184) Li, Y.; Xu, Z.; Xie, M.; Zhang, B.; Li, G.; Luo, W. Resource Recovery from Digested Manure Centrate:
1463 Comparison between Conventional and Aquaporin Thin-Film Composite Forward Osmosis
1464 Membranes. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2020**, *593*, 117436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117436>.
- 1465 (185) Pramanik, B. K.; Hai, F. I.; Ansari, A. J.; Roddick, F. A. Mining Phosphorus from Anaerobically Treated
1466 Dairy Manure by Forward Osmosis Membrane. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* **2019**, *78*,
1467 425–432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2019.05.025>.
- 1468 (186) Wu, Z.; Zou, S.; Zhang, B.; Wang, L.; He, Z. Forward Osmosis Promoted In-Situ Formation of Struvite
1469 with Simultaneous Water Recovery from Digested Swine Wastewater. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2018**,
1470 *342*, 274–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.02.082>.
- 1471 (187) Soler-Cabezas, J. L.; Mendoza-Roca, J. A.; Vincent-Vela, M. C.; Luján-Facundo, M. J.; Pastor-Alcañiz, L.
1472 Simultaneous Concentration of Nutrients from Anaerobically Digested Sludge Centrate and Pre-
1473 Treatment of Industrial Effluents by Forward Osmosis. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2018**, *193*,
1474 289–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2017.10.058>.
- 1475 (188) Ansari, A. J.; Hai, F. I.; Price, W. E.; Nghiem, L. D. Phosphorus Recovery from Digested Sludge Centrate
1476 Using Seawater-Driven Forward Osmosis. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2016**, *163*, 1–7.
1477 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2016.02.031>.
- 1478 (189) Pramanik, B. K.; Shu, L.; Jegatheesan, V. A Review of the Management and Treatment of Brine Solutions.
1479 *Environ. Sci.: Water Res. Technol.* **2017**, *3* (4), 625–658. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6EW00339G>.
- 1480 (190) Morillo, J.; Usero, J.; Rosado, D.; El Bakouri, H.; Riaza, A.; Bernaola, F.-J. Comparative Study of Brine
1481 Management Technologies for Desalination Plants. *Desalination* **2014**, *336*, 32–49.
1482 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2013.12.038>.
- 1483 (191) Panagopoulos, A.; Haralambous, K.-J.; Loizidou, M. Desalination Brine Disposal Methods and
1484 Treatment Technologies - A Review. *Science of The Total Environment* **2019**, *693*, 133545.
1485 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.351>.

- 1486 (192) Giwa, A.; Dufour, V.; Al Marzooqi, F.; Al Kaabi, M.; Hasan, S. W. Brine Management Methods: Recent
1487 Innovations and Current Status. *Desalination* **2017**, *407*, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2016.12.008>.
- 1488 (193) Tang, W.; Ng, H. Y. Concentration of Brine by Forward Osmosis: Performance and Influence of
1489 Membrane Structure. *Desalination* **2008**, *224* (1–3), 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2007.04.085>.
- 1490 (194) Martinetti, C. R.; Childress, A. E.; Cath, T. Y. High Recovery of Concentrated RO Brines Using Forward
1491 Osmosis and Membrane Distillation. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2009**, *331* (1–2), 31–39.
1492 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2009.01.003>.
- 1493 (195) McGinnis, R. L.; Hancock, N. T.; Nowosielski-Slepowron, M. S.; McGurgan, G. D. Pilot Demonstration
1494 of the NH₃/CO₂ Forward Osmosis Desalination Process on High Salinity Brines. *Desalination* **2013**, *312*,
1495 67–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2012.11.032>.
- 1496 (196) Tow, E. W.; McGovern, R. K.; Lienhard V, J. H. Raising Forward Osmosis Brine Concentration Efficiency
1497 through Flow Rate Optimization. *Desalination* **2015**, *366*, 71–79.
1498 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.10.034>.
- 1499 (197) Desalination | Trevi Systems Inc | United States <https://www.trevisystems.com> (accessed Mar 26, 2020).
- 1500 (198) Industrial wastewater <https://www.blue-tec.nl/industrial-wastewater> (accessed Mar 26, 2020).
- 1501 (199) Forward Water Proves Economic Viability of Forward Osmosis Zero Liquid Discharge. *Aquaporin*, 2020.
- 1502 (200) Loganathan, P.; Naidu, G.; Vigneswaran, S. Mining Valuable Minerals from Seawater: A Critical Review.
1503 *Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology* **2017**, *3* (1), 37–53.
1504 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6EW00268D>.
- 1505 (201) Quist-Jensen, C. A.; Ali, A.; Drioli, E.; Macedonio, F. Perspectives on Mining from Sea and Other
1506 Alternative Strategies for Minerals and Water Recovery – The Development of Novel Membrane
1507 Operations. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers* **2019**, *94*, 129–134.
1508 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2018.02.002>.
- 1509 (202) Diallo, M. S.; Kotte, M. R.; Cho, M. Mining Critical Metals and Elements from Seawater: Opportunities
1510 and Challenges. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2015**, *49* (16), 9390–9399. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b00463>.
- 1511 (203) Li, J.; Wang, M.; Zhao, Y.; Yang, H.; Zhong, Y. Enrichment of Lithium from Salt Lake Brine by Forward
1512 Osmosis. *Royal Society open science* **2018**, *5* (10), 180965.
- 1513 (204) Zhou, H. Optimisation of Crystallisation Parameters for Lithium Carbonate Microcrystals Based on
1514 Forward Osmosis (FO) Process. *Materials Research Innovations* **2017**, *21* (1), 1–9.
1515 <https://doi.org/10.1179/1433075X15Y.0000000029>.
- 1516 (205) D’Haese, A. K. H.; De Leersnyder, I.; Vermeir, P.; Verliefde, A. R. D. On Negative Rejection of Uncharged
1517 Organic Solutes in Forward Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2018**, *548*, 22–31.
1518 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.11.002>.
- 1519 (206) Qiu, G.; Wai Wong, G. K.; Ting, Y.-P. Electrostatic Interaction Governed Solute Transport in Forward
1520 Osmosis. *Water Research* **2020**, 115590. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.115590>.
- 1521 (207) Blandin, G.; Verliefde, A. R. D.; Le-Clech, P. Improving Trace Organic Contaminant Rejection Using
1522 Novel Forward Osmosis Membranes; 2015.
- 1523 (208) McCormick, P.; Pellegrino, J.; Mantovani, F.; Sarti, G. Water, Salt, and Ethanol Diffusion through
1524 Membranes for Water Recovery by Forward (Direct) Osmosis Processes. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2008**,
1525 *325* (1), 467–478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2008.08.011>.
- 1526 (209) Sanahuja-Embuena, V.; Khensir, G.; Yusuf, M.; Andersen, M. F.; Nguyen, X. T.; Trzaskus, K.; Pinelo, M.;
1527 Helix-Nielsen, C. Role of Operating Conditions in a Pilot Scale Investigation of Hollow Fiber Forward
1528 Osmosis Membrane Modules. *Membranes* **2019**, *9* (6), 66. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes9060066>.

- 1529 (210) Van Wyk, L. A. Solute Transport in a Submerged Forward Osmosis Membrane System. **2019**.
- 1530 (211) Irvine, G. J.; Rajesh, S.; Georgiadis, M.; Phillip, W. A. Ion Selective Permeation Through Cellulose Acetate
1531 Membranes in Forward Osmosis. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2013**, *47* (23), 13745–13753.
1532 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es403581t>.
- 1533 (212) Lu, X.; Boo, C.; Ma, J.; Elimelech, M. Bidirectional Diffusion of Ammonium and Sodium Cations in
1534 Forward Osmosis: Role of Membrane Active Layer Surface Chemistry and Charge. *Environ. Sci. Technol.*
1535 **2014**, *48* (24), 14369–14376. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es504162v>.
- 1536 (213) Sauchelli, M.; Pellegrino, G.; D’Haese, A.; Rodríguez-Roda, I.; Gernjak, W. Transport of Trace Organic
1537 Compounds through Novel Forward Osmosis Membranes: Role of Membrane Properties and the Draw
1538 Solution. *Water Research* **2018**, *141*, 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.05.003>.
- 1539 (214) Hancock, N. T.; Phillip, W. A.; Elimelech, M.; Cath, T. Y. Bidirectional Permeation of Electrolytes in
1540 Osmotically Driven Membrane Processes. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2011**, *45* (24), 10642–10651.
1541 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es202608y>.
- 1542 (215) Hancock, N. T.; Cath, T. Y. Solute Coupled Diffusion in Osmotically Driven Membrane Processes.
1543 *Environmental Science and Technology* **2009**, *43* (17), 6769–6775.
- 1544 (216) Yaroshchuk, A.; Bruening, M. L.; Licón Bernal, E. E. Solution-Diffusion–Electro-Migration Model and Its
1545 Uses for Analysis of Nanofiltration, Pressure-Retarded Osmosis and Forward Osmosis in Multi-Ionic
1546 Solutions. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2013**, *447*, 463–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.07.047>.
- 1547 (217) D’Haese, A. K. H. Interactions between Feed Solutes and Inorganic Electrolytic Draw Solutes in Forward
1548 Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2020**, *597*, 117636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117636>.
- 1549 (218) Xie, M.; Nghiem, L. D.; Price, W. E.; Elimelech, M. Comparison of the Removal of Hydrophobic Trace
1550 Organic Contaminants by Forward Osmosis and Reverse Osmosis. *Water Research* **2012**, *46* (8), 2683–
1551 2692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2012.02.023>.
- 1552 (219) Jin, X.; Shan, J.; Wang, C.; Wei, J.; Tang, C. Y. Rejection of Pharmaceuticals by Forward Osmosis
1553 Membranes. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* **2012**, *227–228*, 55–61.
1554 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2012.04.077>.
- 1555 (220) Verliefde, A. R. D.; Van der Meeren, P.; Van der Bruggen, B.; Hoek, E. M. V.; Tarabara, V. V. Solution-
1556 Diffusion Processes. In *Encyclopedia of Membrane Science and Technology*; John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2013.
- 1557 (221) Farhat, A.; Ahmad, F.; Hilal, N.; Arafat, H. A. Boron Removal in New Generation Reverse Osmosis (RO)
1558 Membranes Using Two-Pass RO without PH Adjustment. *Desalination* **2013**, *310*, 50–59.
1559 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2012.10.003>.
- 1560 (222) Jin, X.; Tang, C. Y.; Gu, Y.; She, Q.; Qi, S. Boric Acid Permeation in Forward Osmosis Membrane
1561 Processes: Modeling, Experiments, and Implications. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2011**, *45* (6), 2323–2330.
1562 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es103771a>.
- 1563 (223) Jin, X.; She, Q.; Ang, X.; Tang, C. Y. Removal of Boron and Arsenic by Forward Osmosis Membrane:
1564 Influence of Membrane Orientation and Organic Fouling. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2012**, *389*, 182–187.
1565 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.10.028>.
- 1566 (224) Luo, L.; Zhou, Z.; Chung, T.-S.; Weber, M.; Staudt, C.; Maletzko, C. Experiments and Modeling of Boric
1567 Acid Permeation through Double-Skinned Forward Osmosis Membranes. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2016**, *50*
1568 (14), 7696–7705. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b06166>.
- 1569 (225) Valladares Linares, R.; Li, Z. Y.; Sarp, S.; Park, Y. G.; Amy, G.; Vrouwenvelder, J. S. Higher Boron
1570 Rejection with a New TFC Forward Osmosis Membrane. *Desalination and Water Treatment* **2014**.

- 1571 (226) Wang, Y.-N.; Li, W.; Wang, R.; Tang, C. Y. Enhancing Boron Rejection in FO Using Alkaline Draw
1572 Solutions. *Water Research* **2017**, *118*, 20–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.04.016>.
- 1573 (227) Coday, B. D.; Heil, D. M.; Xu, P.; Cath, T. Y. Effects of Transmembrane Hydraulic Pressure on
1574 Performance of Forward Osmosis Membranes. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2013**, *47* (5), 2386–2393.
1575 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es304519p>.
- 1576 (228) Jafarinejad, S.; Park, H.; Mayton, H.; Walker, S. L.; Jiang, S. C. Concentrating Ammonium in Wastewater
1577 by Forward Osmosis Using a Surface Modified Nanofiltration Membrane. *Environ. Sci.: Water Res.*
1578 *Technol.* **2019**, *5* (2), 246–255. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EW00690C>.
- 1579 (229) FLUID TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS, INC. - Products <http://ftsh2o.com/products/> (accessed Apr 8,
1580 2020).
- 1581 (230) Kim, J.; Blandin, G.; Phuntsho, S.; Verliefe, A.; Le-Clech, P.; Shon, H. Practical Considerations for
1582 Operability of an 8" Spiral Wound Forward Osmosis Module: Hydrodynamics, Fouling Behaviour and
1583 Cleaning Strategy. *Desalination* **2017**, *404*, 249–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2016.11.004>.
- 1584 (231) Poriferanano. Element packing density comparison.
- 1585 (232) Saito, K.; Irie, M.; Zaito, S.; Sakai, H.; Hayashi, H.; Tanioka, A. Power Generation with Salinity Gradient
1586 by Pressure Retarded Osmosis Using Concentrated Brine from SWRO System and Treated Sewage as
1587 Pure Water. *Desalination and Water Treatment* **2012**, *41* (1–3), 114–121.
1588 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2012.664696>.
- 1589 (233) Aquaporin. Aquaporin Inside™ Forward Osmosis membrane products.
- 1590 (234) Berghof Membranes and Aquaporin Take next Step in Tubular FO. *berghofmembranes.com*, 2018.
- 1591 (235) Blandin, G.; Rodriguez-Roda, I.; Comas, J. Submerged Osmotic Processes: Design and Operation to
1592 Mitigate Mass Transfer Limitations. *Membranes* **2018**, *8* (3), 72.
1593 <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes8030072>.
- 1594 (236) Spier, M. R.; Vandenberghe, L. P. D. S.; Medeiros, A. B. P.; Soccol, C. R. Application of Different Types
1595 of Bioreactors in Bioprocesses. In *Bioreactors: Design, Properties and Applications*; 2011; pp 53–87.
- 1596 (237) Lian, B.; Blandin, G.; Leslie, G.; Le-Clech, P. Impact of Module Design in Forward Osmosis and Pressure
1597 Assisted Osmosis: An Experimental and Numerical Study. *Desalination* **2018**, *426*, 108–117.
1598 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2017.10.047>.
- 1599 (238) Gruber, M. F.; Aslak, U.; Hélix-Nielsen, C. Open-Source CFD Model for Optimization of Forward
1600 Osmosis and Reverse Osmosis Membrane Modules. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2016**, *158*, 183–
1601 192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2015.12.017>.
- 1602 (239) Xiao, D.; Li, W.; Chou, S.; Wang, R.; Tang, C. Y. A Modeling Investigation on Optimizing the Design of
1603 Forward Osmosis Hollow Fiber Modules. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2012**, *392–393*, 76–87.
1604 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.12.006>.
- 1605 (240) Kim, Y. C.; Park, S.-J. Experimental Study of a 4040 Spiral-Wound Forward-Osmosis Membrane Module.
1606 *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **2011**, *45* (18), 7737–7745. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es202175m>.
- 1607 (241) Bilad, M. R. Module-Scale Simulation of Forward Osmosis Module-Part A: Plate-and-Frame. *IJOST* **2016**,
1608 *1* (2), 249. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijost.v1i2.3810>.
- 1609 (242) Bilad, M. R. Module-Scale Simulation of Forward Osmosis Module-Part B: Modified Spiral-Wound.
1610 *IJOST* **2017**, *2* (2), 211. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijost.v2i2.7998>.
- 1611 (243) Deshmukh, A.; Yip, N. Y.; Lin, S.; Elimelech, M. Desalination by Forward Osmosis: Identifying
1612 Performance Limiting Parameters through Module-Scale Modeling. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**,
1613 *491*, 159–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.03.080>.

- 1614 (244) Gu, B.; Kim, D. Y.; Kim, J. H.; Yang, D. R. Mathematical Model of Flat Sheet Membrane Modules for FO
1615 Process: Plate-and-Frame Module and Spiral-Wound Module. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2011**, *379* (1–
1616 2), 403–415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.06.012>.
- 1617 (245) Qing, L.; Bilad, M. R.; Sun, G.; Jaafar, J.; Fane, A. G. Flow Uneven-Distribution and Its Impact on
1618 Performances of Forward Osmosis Module. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* **2020**, *33*, 101014.
1619 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2019.101014>.
- 1620 (246) Membrane Modules <http://www.porifera.com/modules> (accessed Apr 20, 2020).
- 1621 (247) Phuntsho, S.; Hong, S.; Elimelech, M.; Shon, H. K. Osmotic Equilibrium in the Forward Osmosis Process:
1622 Modelling, Experiments and Implications for Process Performance. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, *453*,
1623 240–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.11.009>.
- 1624 (248) Sahebi, S.; Phuntsho, S.; Eun Kim, J.; Hong, S.; Kyong Shon, H. Pressure Assisted Fertiliser Drawn
1625 Osmosis Process to Enhance Final Dilution of the Fertiliser Draw Solution beyond Osmotic Equilibrium.
1626 *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**, *481*, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.01.055>.
- 1627 (249) Ge, Q.; Ling, M.; Chung, T.-S. Draw Solutions for Forward Osmosis Processes: Developments,
1628 Challenges, and Prospects for the Future. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2013**, *442*, 225–237.
1629 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.03.046>.
- 1630 (250) Long, Q.; Jia, Y.; Li, J.; Yang, J.; Liu, F.; Zheng, J.; Yu, B. Recent Advance on Draw Solutes Development
1631 in Forward Osmosis. *Processes* **2018**, *6* (9), 165. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr6090165>.
- 1632 (251) Guide to Commercial Draw Solutions | ForwardOsmosisTech.
- 1633 (252) Corzo, B.; de la Torre, T.; Sans, C.; Ferrero, E.; Malfeito, J. J. Evaluation of Draw Solutions and
1634 Commercially Available Forward Osmosis Membrane Modules for Wastewater Reclamation at Pilot
1635 Scale. *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2017**, *326*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.05.108>.
- 1636 (253) De la torre, T.; Arnaldos, M.; Corzo, B.; Navea, S.; Ferrero, Enrique; Bacarit, J.; Malfeito, J. Evaluation of
1637 FO for Wastewater Reclamation with a Focus on the Selection of Optimal Draw Solutions, 2014.
- 1638 (254) Siddiqui, F. A.; She, Q.; Fane, A. G.; Field, R. W. Exploring the Differences between Forward Osmosis
1639 and Reverse Osmosis Fouling. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2018**, *565*, 241–253.
1640 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2018.08.034>.
- 1641 (255) Xie, M.; Lee, J.; Nghiem, L. D.; Elimelech, M. Role of Pressure in Organic Fouling in Forward Osmosis
1642 and Reverse Osmosis. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**, *493*, 748–754.
1643 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.07.033>.
- 1644 (256) Blandin, G.; Verliefe, A. R. D.; Le-Clech, P. Pressure Enhanced Fouling and Adapted Anti-Fouling
1645 Strategy in Pressure Assisted Osmosis (PAO). *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**, *493*, 557–567.
1646 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2015.07.014>.
- 1647 (257) Sauchelli Toran, M.; D’Haese, A.; Rodríguez-Roda, I.; Gernjak, W. Fouling Propensity of Novel TFC
1648 Membranes with Different Osmotic and Hydraulic Pressure Driving Forces. *Water Research* **2020**, *175*,
1649 115657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.115657>.
- 1650 (258) Blandin, G.; Vervoort, H.; Le-Clech, P.; Verliefe, A. R. D. Fouling and Cleaning of High Permeability
1651 Forward Osmosis Membranes. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* **2016**, *9*, 161–169.
1652 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2015.12.007>.
- 1653 (259) Nguyen, T.-T.; Kook, S.; Lee, C.; Field, R. W.; Kim, I. S. Critical Flux-Based Membrane Fouling Control
1654 of Forward Osmosis: Behavior, Sustainability, and Reversibility. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2019**, *570–*
1655 *571*, 380–393. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2018.10.062>.

- 1656 (260) Mi, B.; Elimelech, M. Organic Fouling of Forward Osmosis Membranes: Fouling Reversibility and
1657 Cleaning without Chemical Reagents. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2010**, *348* (1–2), 337–345.
1658 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2009.11.021>.
- 1659 (261) Wang, Z.; Tang, J.; Zhu, C.; Dong, Y.; Wang, Q.; Wu, Z. Chemical Cleaning Protocols for Thin Film
1660 Composite (TFC) Polyamide Forward Osmosis Membranes Used for Municipal Wastewater Treatment.
1661 *Journal of Membrane Science* **2015**, *475*, 184–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.10.032>.
- 1662 (262) Linares, R. V.; Li, Z.; Yangali-Quintanilla, V.; Li, Q.; Amy, G. Cleaning Protocol for a FO Membrane
1663 Fouled in Wastewater Reuse. *Desalination and Water Treatment* **2013**, *51* (25–27), 4821–4824.
1664 <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2013.795345>.
- 1665 (263) Low, K. S. Vibration-Assisted Forward Osmosis Process for Mitigation of Concentration Polarization in
1666 Submerged Hollow Fiber Membrane System. **2019**.
- 1667 (264) Aslan, M.; Saatçi, Y.; Hanay, Ö.; Hasar, H. Effect of Biogas Sparging with Different Membrane Modules
1668 on Membrane Fouling in Anaerobic Submerged Membrane Bioreactor (AnSMBR). *Environ Sci Pollut Res*
1669 **2014**, *21* (5), 3285–3293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-013-2303-8>.
- 1670 (265) Motsa, M. M.; Mamba, B. B.; Thwala, J. M.; Verliefde, A. R. D. Osmotic Backwash of Fouled FO
1671 Membranes: Cleaning Mechanisms and Membrane Surface Properties after Cleaning. *Desalination* **2017**,
1672 *402*, 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2016.09.018>.
- 1673 (266) Antony, A.; Low, J. H.; Gray, S.; Childress, A. E.; Le-Clech, P.; Leslie, G. Scale Formation and Control in
1674 High Pressure Membrane Water Treatment Systems: A Review. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2011**, *383* (1–
1675 2), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2011.08.054>.
- 1676 (267) Phuntsho, S.; Lotfi, F.; Hong, S.; Shaffer, D. L.; Elimelech, M.; Shon, H. K. Membrane Scaling and Flux
1677 Decline during Fertiliser-Drawn Forward Osmosis Desalination of Brackish Groundwater. *Water*
1678 *Research* **2014**, *57*, 172–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2014.03.034>.
- 1679 (268) Mi, B.; Elimelech, M. Silica Scaling and Scaling Reversibility in Forward Osmosis. *Desalination* **2013**, *312*,
1680 75–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2012.08.034>.
- 1681 (269) Zhang, M.; Hou, D.; She, Q.; Tang, C. Y. Gypsum Scaling in Pressure Retarded Osmosis: Experiments,
1682 Mechanisms and Implications. *Water Research* **2014**, *48*, 387–395.
1683 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2013.09.051>.
- 1684 (270) Zhang, M. Influence of Feed and Draw Solutions Chemistry on Scaling in Osmotically Driven Membrane
1685 Process. *School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore* **2015**.
- 1686 (271) Oren, S.; Birnhack, L.; Lehmann, O.; Lahav, O. A Different Approach for Brackish-Water Desalination,
1687 Comprising Acidification of the Feed-Water and CO₂(Aq) Reuse for Alkalinity, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ Supply
1688 in the Post Treatment Stage. *Separation and Purification Technology* **2012**, *89*, 252–260.
1689 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2012.01.027>.
- 1690 (272) Liu, Y.; Mi, B. Combined Fouling of Forward Osmosis Membranes: Synergistic Foulant Interaction and
1691 Direct Observation of Fouling Layer Formation. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2012**, *407–408*, 136–144.
1692 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2012.03.028>.
- 1693 (273) Liu, Y.; Mi, B. Effects of Organic Macromolecular Conditioning on Gypsum Scaling of Forward Osmosis
1694 Membranes. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2014**, *450*, 153–161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2013.09.001>.
- 1695 (274) Zhang, J.; Loong, W. L. C.; Chou, S.; Tang, C.; Wang, R.; Fane, A. G. Membrane Biofouling and Scaling
1696 in Forward Osmosis Membrane Bioreactor. *Journal of Membrane Science* **2012**, *403–404*, 8–14.
1697 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2012.01.032>.
- 1698

© 2020 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).